

National and International Environmental Law and Justice

The Unresolved Issues

6. Biopiracy-Bioprospecting-Bicolonisation-Scientific Colonization

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Biopiracy, together with its other tentacles, '*bioprospecting*' and '*biocolonisation*' happens when researchers, research organizations or businesses appropriate biological resources, largely from less affluent countries or marginalised people, without official sanction. It is not limited to drug development as often is the case, but also occurs in agricultural and industrial contexts.

The Oxford dictionary defines biopiracy as:

The practice of commercially exploiting naturally occurring biochemical or genetic material, especially by obtaining patents that restrict its future use, while failing to pay fair compensation to the community from which it originates.

There are several definitions of biopiracy, all meaning the same, and the definition proposed by Robinson (2010) states that:

The act of taking living things, especially plants from an area or taking the knowledge of local people about these living things, and using them or it to make money for a particular company or organisation.

Whereas Rose Janna of '*The Conversation*' (2016) defines biopiracy as:

Biopiracy (also known as scientific colonialism) is defined as the unauthorized appropriation of knowledge and genetic resources of farming and indigenous communities by individuals or institutions seeking exclusive monopoly control through patents or intellectual property.

All definitions centre on appropriation of bioresources and knowledge regarding such resources, otherwise an activity regarded as both unethical and illegal. To describe and define the theft or misappropriation of genetic resources and traditional knowledge through the intellectual property system, Pat Mooney (2000) coined the term '*biopiracy*,' and Mooney further added that it also encompasses unauthorized and uncompensated collection of genetic resources for commercial purposes, in other words, including '*bioprospecting*.'

The analysis of Daniel Robinson (2010), as supported by others, reveals three common defining characteristics of biopiracy:

1. It concerns genetic resources and knowledge associated with those resources;
2. It concerns resources collected from '*farming and Indigenous communities*;'
3. It uses patents and other forms of intellectual property rights (IPR) to control and monopolize such resources.

However, Robinson does not mention collection of plants, plant materials and genetic resources from the uninhabited wild, where local authorities have little surveillance or monitoring systems in place, or the role of corruption often associated with the practice.

Concluding his discussion, Robinson however further states that:

Biopiracy refers to an illegitimate appropriation of locally held knowledge by non-local commercial actors. It is most often associated with western biotech companies who forage the fauna and flora of biodiversity rich developing countries to exploit and commercialize biological substances that have been used by Indigenous people for generations.

Discussing the meaning and occurrence of biopiracy or bioprospecting from the point of view of Robinson (2010), that is the practice of '*illegitimate appropriations*,' Alejandro Madrazo (2013), argues that the illegality of the activities should not be considered in isolation with current laws that actually condone such appropriations, and emphasize that:

Since piracy is an illegal activity or an activity at the margins of the law, modern bioprospecting is a practice that is enabled precisely by the specific rules of current intellectual property law.

To take the comments of Madrazo more seriously, there is a need to understand that these same '*intellectual property laws*' have been concocted by countries of the North for these same countries, heavily influenced by Multi National Companies (MNCs) and capitalism, with little or no input from countries of the South; thus, the first flaw that diminishes the reality of the argument.

Given that biopiracy and its allies bioprospecting and biocolonisation are invariably associated with the exploitative activities of multinational corporations, Breske (2018) defines biopiracy as:

The practice of economic exploitation by powerful multinational corporations (MNCs) that take on the identity and power structures of nation states, with established laws protecting the corporations that obtain patents or intellectual property rights more readily than the original indigenous knowledge-holders.

According to Breske, the definition holds true when biopiracy through both bioprospecting and biocolonisation arise from the persisting dominant practices and beliefs of neoliberal colonialism supporting economic practices around the world, and more specifically in the Global North. Breske further contends that:

This form of colonialism is based on the exploitation and extraction of traditional resources and knowledge through Western conceptions of property ownership.

In associating biopiracy with colonialism, it becomes clear that biopiracy is simply an invention and practice of capitalism to appropriate both resources and knowledge. In an earlier discussion, Wolf (2007) contends that privatizing nature and knowledge is the expected result of the development of the power of capitalism into monopoly capitalism, rather than an objective related to earlier imperialistic forms of colonization, and the author defines the situation as:

The stage in capitalism where all industries are controlled by a few producers acting in concert to maximize profits through cornered markets.

Wolf finds that what accompanies the practice is a dual injustice of theft and crimes, so far not fully addressed by international legal systems. On the other hand, the observations of Vedantu of India (2021) claim that:

Because biopiracy is a fresh type of crime that only developed two decades ago, there has been no legislation to penalise it. Another factor is that developed countries have dominated the major international agreements and are dictating the rules as a result.

Vedantu (2021) goes even further in explaining the cause and effect of biopiracy in its present context:

Biopiracy's current supremacy in the modern world may be seen as an outgrowth of neoliberalism's political and economic ideology and in many ways a modern politico-economic theory which favours free trade, privatization, minimal government intervention in business.

A number of scholars propose that biopiracy is also historically rooted in colonialism, mainly based on the concept of *Terra Nullius*, discussed by Ferris (2004). Consequently, such top commodities like sugar, pepper, quinine and coffee were all taken from formerly colonized countries via Western trading companies that plundered local ecologies for profit, and the historical, social and economic implications of these past practices have been analyzed and discussed by Mulligan and Stott (2000).

Referring to the concept of *Terra Nullius*, Robinson (2010, 2015) contends that biopiracy is often regarded as an extension, and in some aspects an intensification of a colonial system of exploitation, similar to the perception of Ferris (2004), and the revelations of Mulligan and Stott (2000). Bringing back useful biological substances from the colonies has a long history, but the expansion of intellectual property rights, and particularly of patents, adds a new dimension to it, explains Robinson. The contention of Vedantu (2021) that biopiracy is also historically rooted in imperialist model of colonialism further supports the arguments of Robinson.

Basing his arguments on the historical context and aspects of imperialism and colonization, the *Terra Nullius* concept, and the discussion of Mulligan and Stott (2000), Robinson (2015) adds a further dimension to the definition of biopiracy as:

An extension, or even an intensification of colonial exploitation of natural resources, bringing back useful biological substances from the colonies.

The arguments of Robinson obviously points to a new phenomenon: neocolonisation through economic colonization. Over the last decades or so, biopiracy has become a high-ranking global justice issue since it directly relates to neo-colonialist modes of exploitation enforced through economic instruments embodied in international trade institutions and agreements like the Trade Related Aspects of Intellectual Property agreement (TRIPS), which requires all WTO-members to implement certain Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) standards in their national legislation. Both of these appear to have been either inadvertently or purposely enhanced through the dilution of rights imposed by the Convention of Biological Diversity (CBD-1992) and the Nagoya Protocol (2010).

The effectiveness of the Nagoya has been questioned too often. Discussing biopiracy after analyzing the essence of the Nagoya Protocol, and as a reflection of the view of many scholars, Rabitz (2015) argues that:

Biopiracy being a particularly malignant and most of the time illegal practice resulting from distributional conflicts between (private) users and provider countries or communities, the Protocol emphasizes compliance management over enforcement, which obviously will likely be insufficient to ensure fair and equitable benefit-sharing in those cases where commercial stakes are involved.

However, under which instruments should compliance and enforcement be assigned remains vague, and should hardly be a subject of arguments. In their discussions about the international legality of TRIPS, Drahos and Braithwaite (2002) describe TRIPS as an

instrument for the developed countries to legally impose their Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) agenda on the developing world; in other words a form of legal enforcement of neo-colonialism. The authors reflect on biopiracy in the following terms:

The epidemic of biopiracy is an assault on our living heritage of biodiversity and cumulative innovation embodied in the traditional knowledge of agriculture and medicine. It is the governments duty to protect the resources and heritage of the country and prevent its usurpation by foreign interests and commercial corporations.

Biopiracy is not limited to '*usurpation*' of indigenous knowledge and traditional resources. It can extend to the genetic material of populations. It is interesting to note that genetic resources are also subject to patent laws, the intricacies and complexities of which have been analyzed and discussed in the thesis of Brown (2005). The author explains how the Human Genome Diversity Project (HGDP), dubbed the '*Vampire Project*,' has not received the approval of indigenous communities, and raised serious legal, ethical and moral objections from human rights advocates, with many issues of bioethical concerns including:

- The possibility of commercial exploitation through gene patenting, and,
- The Project's insulting rhetoric of extinction and preservation.

Brown, (2005) claims the concept of research under the guise of helping humanity is another iteration of biopiracy leading to '*biocolonialism*,' since the main objective is the '*mining*' of the DNA of indigenous peoples. The discussions of Smith (2012) further elaborate on the objectivity of the Project, concluding that it is yet another of the many aspects of piracy and '*scientific research colonialism*.' Far from being simply '*scientific research*,' the Project aims at turning humans into objects, and maybe even commodifying humans too.

Probably the most famous example of biopiracy is the United States patent issued for the Indian spice Turmeric. The Indian Council for Scientific and Industrial Research opposed the patent based on lack of either discovery or novelty since Turmeric has been traditionally used in India for centuries. The patent was eventually revoked, but not until the Indian government spent nearly \$6 million fighting the patents for both Turmeric and Neem-based medicines.

Reid (2009) mentions a similar case where the pharmaceutical company Eli Lilly, one of the first drug companies accused of biopiracy, developed two drugs from the rosy periwinkle, found in abundance as an endemic plant species on the island-nation of Madagascar. These drugs, *vinblastine* and *vincristine*, used in the treatment of Hodgkin's disease and childhood leukemia respectively, earned Eli Lilly \$100 million and neither Madagascar nor the indigenous inhabitants, the rightful owners of the plant species, obtained any royalties or share of the profits.

Those few examples, among thousands of others, illustrate one of the largest problems with biopiracy, an unethical and illegal practice, most of which goes unnoticed, not documented or published, and the limited amount published not compiled and difficult to find.

In his analysis, Reid (2009) contends that since traditional knowledge does not rise to a level where it could be patented, and since indigenous peoples do not generally have the means to conduct further research themselves, rich companies with the means could team with them to attempt new discoveries. However, that route has never been attempted since biopiracy and bioprospecting are shorter, cheaper, and more profitable routes, and imposition of terms on weaker nations and communities too easy.

Impositions to justify appropriations are neither legal, nor ethical, nor moral. The arguments of Drahos and Braithwaite (2002) have been further elaborated upon by Shiva (2007; 2008) in her discussion on the controversy of biopiracy in India, explaining that:

Through biopiracy, outside corporations and nations can quickly take resources and secure their control through international intellectual property rights and patents. The legitimation for these corporations stems from this westernized, neoliberal economy and the reduction in trade barriers that benefits the wealthier areas of the world at the expense of marginalized peoples.

The situation in India, as discussed by Shiva, is not much different from what exists in other countries of Asia, Africa or S. America. Such illegal activities appear to be to this day only sanctioned by inadequate soft laws, and protected by trade agreements tailor-made to suit corporations, a situation allowed to persist because of the lack of appropriate and effective human rights, criminal, or environmental laws. Analyzing and discussing the extensive reach of the exploitative activities of corporate activities, Nigel South (2007; 2017) contends that:

Corporate biopiracy and the process by which the transnational mobility of corporations facilitates the transfer of knowledge and rights from their indigenous origins to legally protected, private and profit-oriented intellectual property monopolizers operate in a mafia-like network.

Rather than addressing the criminal activities embodied within biopiracy/bioprospecting, some scholars, especially environmentalist, prefer to divert discussions into conservation and environmental protection to justify them. In other words, to '*camouflage environmental crimes into legal conservation activities.*' Such rather simplistic and erroneous views, sometimes common in conservation arguments regarding the unlawful destruction and depletion of natural resources for profit, including rare plants that could eventually become extinct may go unnoticed, or even overlooked. There have been claims that appropriate legal tools should be available to protect them, without however discussing how the cause should be brought under control through legal environmental prescriptions. The discussions of Barnett (2006) emphasizes on such a simplistic view in declaring that there could be environmental implications, since if local people do not profit or benefit from their own environment and natural resources, they have less incentive to preserve its biodiversity, which may lead to environmental harm and degradation. The argument is more of an assumption that biopiracy/bioprospecting helps biodiversity conservation.

However, Boekhout van Solinge (2010) and Wilder et al. (2016) consider such observations regarding biodiversity conservation and the role of indigenous communities at odds with the findings of studies that have analyzed in details how corporations totally disregard the environment, whether human or natural. Environmental destruction occurs alongside the imposition of unfair monopolies of trade based on patents, with the consequence that rare plant and animal species are appropriated simply for profit, and overexploited to the point of extinction, contend the authors.

The arguments of Barnett (2006) obviously ignore that the reality of such a prospect lies in the unabated appropriation and expropriation of bioresources. However, what Barnett also fails to realize is that indigenous populations have been avid conservationists of their biodiversity and biological resources even before the birth of conservation science and conservation organizations, a role recognized by Claudia Sobrevilla of the World Bank (2008), Siham Drissi of UNEP (2020), and several other international conservation organizations. What indigenous communities never expected is that such resources would be pirated, and no appropriate laws would be formulated against biopirating.

Eisner, T. (1990), Eisner, M. (2004) and Butler (2014) are the few of the conservationists arguing that corporate behaviour should first and foremost be more seriously regulated for the benefit of the environment, rather than attempting to regulate the behaviour of indigenous farmers or land users. Hayden (2003) claims that biopiracy is simply an institutionalized practice garnering transnational capital, and the argument is that it helps in opening of the market on biodiversity as both a development strategy and a strategy for conservation within an economic framework is pure whitewash. Data on that assumption proves otherwise.

The discussion of Mackey and Liang (2012) analyse how global governance has been ineffective in protecting biodiversity from biopiracy, '*in spite of the fact that potentially useful medicines arise from developing countries*' biodiverse environments and indigenous knowledge. What are blatantly lacking are appropriate mechanisms within existing frameworks of environmental law for the protection of biodiversity, not necessarily as a common good, but as private property. The authors find that global intellectual property rules have raised serious ethical concerns of environmental justice, modes of exploitation, and health disparities in these populations, mainly as a result of minimum intellectual property standards established by the rules.

Mackey and Liang further explain how these global IPR systems focus specifically on patent systems and private economic development under the World Trade Organization (WTO) TRIPS regime, and on the biased prescriptions of the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO). Similar to the earlier conclusions of Shiva (1997), the authors claim that such an array of rules, invariably concocted by the North for the developed countries of the north, have failed to protect indigenous rights, promote access to life-saving/profit-oriented drugs within transparent legal frameworks, prevent biopiracy, or provide for responsible biodiversity protection, utilization and development.

Criminilising biopiracy has also been a subject of discussions, as evidenced in the work of Popovski and Turner (2008). With the realization that biopiracy should be regarded as a crime, a UN report on '*The Globalisation of Crime*' from the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (2010), points out that '*trafficking of environmental resources*' is now a key challenge for some developing nations. The UN report concludes that apart from the activities of biopirates, other problems may arise, including:

Many emerging economies are based on exporting raw materials, but under-resourced governments may lack the capacity to regulate the exploitation of these assets. Rather than promoting economic progress, poorly managed natural wealth can become a cause of bad governance, corruption, or even violent conflict.

Whether biopiracy should be simply defined as, '*trafficking of environmental resources*' is highly debatable. While the UN appears to concentrate on regulating bad governance, little effort appears to emanate from the UN to regulate the criminal activities of biopirates and bioprospectors. Bad governance has no doubt crept into both developing states and even indigenous communities, and the willing teachers have been no less than the perpetrators of biopiracy themselves. The UN appears to dilute the seriousness of the scourge by referring to '*exportation of raw material,*' rather than '*illegal appropriation,*' steering clear of the use of the terms '*biopiracy*' or '*bioprospecting,*' or '*biocolonisation.*' As such, the UN fails to elaborate whether such exportation is between '*willing seller and willing buyer,*' or simply forcibly and illegally removed without authorization, or though corruption, bribery and coercion.

What should also be important to consider is that multinational corporations are forever busy corrupting governments of weaker economies, discussed in details by Roberto Ferdman of the Washington Post (2014). Revelations about the existence and common practice of such corrupt activities associated with biopiracy and bioprospecting fall well within the precincts of green criminology and human environmental rights, as proposed by South and Brisman (2013), White and Heckenberg (2014), and Goyes and South (2016)

Why perpetrators of biopiracy resort to criminal activities has been explained by the gainful financial returns. Being primarily associated with the pharmaceutical industry, but not necessarily the only one, biopiracy has become a growing problem due to the soaring sales of pharmaceuticals, explains Businesswire in a 2022 report. The value of the world market for medicinal plants was worth an estimated \$1.2 trillion at ex-factory prices in 2020, reveals Businesswire (2022). Obtaining traditional knowledge increases the efficiency of the screening process for plants with medicinal properties by more than four hundred percent, which is why indigenous peoples' knowledge is so valuable to the industry, remarks Reid (2009). Without formal legal protection for indigenous communities, biopiracy is often a shortcut to massive profits without having to provide fair compensation to the original sources of either the raw material or the information, as explained in the discussions of Shiva (2007) and Reid (2009). However, and according to Stiglitz (1999) the contention that knowledge should be a public good, that is free for the taking, persists within several international circles.

There is little doubt that the global demand for medicinal drugs has led to an increase in biopiracy in the Global South. Once companies find something they believe will be profitable, they want to patent it straightaway so that no one else can capitalize off it. Patents are an easily accessible source of income for those able to apply for them. In fact, patents act as an exclusive control on a product, and when corporations hold patents on biodiversity, they are creating a monopoly on food and health too, claims Reid (2009) and Imran et al. (2021).

The analysis of Wyatt (2015; 2021) exposes how Western institutions perpetuate and legitimise the exploitation of indigenous knowledge through a biased globalised patent system and specific view of intellectual property, since the global patent system created by Western developed nations only recognise certain forms of '*proof*' of knowledge. Wyatt concludes that:

Denial of biopiracy makes it invisible to not only the indigenous communities who are victims of it, but also to the global community

In some ways, it is impossible for those in developing countries to compete with MNCs due to how patents and intellectual property rights are sustained. Since patents are held nationally instead of internationally, most patent holders tend to be from more developed countries. Because of this divide, it is possible to inflate the price of patented medicines so that corporations can make an even greater profit, which leads to more global inequalities explains Imran et al. (2021). Another added factor is that they are also given legal and state protection through their infinite political and legal resources and act as decentralized global forces, a system that is out of reach and unaffordable to either ordinary people or indigenous populations, explain the authors.

The publications of Vandana Shiva (1993, 1997, 2007, 2008, 2020) elaborate on how the Global North has a detrimental impact on the Global South's environment and traditional systems of food cultivation and societal relationships. Biodiversity and Biotechnology, argues

Shiva, have given rise to a new term in the language of the commons: biopiracy, notwithstanding that biopiracy is actually the exploitative appropriation, or '*the plunder of nature and knowledge*,' which today is looked upon as normal business activities well outside the frameworks of laws, environmental or criminal. However, counterclaims have been made by some researchers and most corporations; otherwise, '*biopirates*' argue that bioprospecting is for the common good and it creates '*hybrid knowledges by implementing indigenous practices and knowledges into Western understandings of capital*,' a statement strongly contested and discussed further by Shiva (1997) and Breske, (2017; 2018).

Additionally and in agreement with Shiva, Breske claims that the general consensus about biopiracy is that it continually enhances the colonial dynamics for marginalized or indigenous peoples of the south through the extraction of knowledge or resources, and reduces hopes for altering the power imbalance, an argument to which Hayden (2003) pertinently adds that:

Indigenous activists, engaged ethnoscientists and legal scholars, and nongovernmental organizations have thus attempted to pry open the exclusive hold that Northern, corporate entities have had on intellectual property rights.

Wirtén (2008) adds to the discussion about the South-North movement of resources through biopiracy and proposes that what is involved and not to be neglected should be the fact that it not only concerns a geopolitical South-North movement of plants and genetic resources, but also of a South-North movement of knowledge. In support of the proposition of Wirtén, in an earlier discussion Mgbeoji (2006) expounds on the South-North traffic of genetic materials and knowledge, observing that:

The ongoing global and local corporate practice of asserting the right of ownership over genetic materials taken from living organisms, including the patenting of medicines, seeds, plants and even more developed forms of life, and the appropriation of knowledge and nature (Biopiracy), is invariably from the '*South*' to the '*North*'.

Ryan and Green (2015) further adds to available information on biopiracy and discuss how the international community has pushed back against curtailing or controlling it through appropriate legal prescriptions, except through some dubious soft laws. To control the scourge, several countries and international bodies are creating databases of traditional knowledge, hoping to preclude appropriation through the issuance of patents on that knowledge. Other countries, including Thailand, have extended intellectual property protection to the traditional knowledge stakeholders themselves, and that for reasons mentioned by the authors as being:

For decades, Eastern traditional medicine has been misappropriated by others who claim it as their own and attempted to obtain patent protection for it.

In other words, Thailand openly declares that its bioresources have been pirated for too long, and the time has come to restore the same to their rightful owners. In her thesis '*Reclaiming the Commons: Biodiversity, Indigenous Knowledge, and the Rights of Mother Earth*,' Shiva (2020) elaborates on the scientific, legal, political, and cultural struggle to defend the sovereignty of biodiversity and indigenous knowledge to this day and declares that:

Corporate war on nature and people through patents and corporate Intellectual Property Rights has unleashed an epidemic of biopiracy resulting in important legal battles fighting efforts to patent the rights to many plants

It is however not in recent times that some states, mainly in the South, have started reacting against biopiracy/bioprospecting or appropriation of indigenous knowledge. As far back as (2005), ETCO (Brazilian Institute of Ethics in Competition commented on how the federal

government of Brazil was preparing a bill designed to curb biopiracy and legislate on the fate of biopirates acting almost unpunished in Brazilian forests. One of the main objectives was to classify the crime of biopiracy, which currently does not exist in the country's laws. Because of the legal vacuum, the practice has been punished only based on the law on environmental crimes, whose penalties are relatively too mild to prevent recurrence. Such a '*legal vacuum*' has been the basis of numerous discussion, and the propositions of Goyes et al. (2017) and Wyatt and Brisman (2017) and others to resort to hard laws within the context of green criminology for effective control are being seriously considered as the obvious alternative to soft laws.

However, the long struggle to curtail such an '*epidemic*' and its associated tentacles is facing too many hurdles. According to Wyatt, the '*invisibility*' of the harms produced by biopiracy is increased by the remoteness of the locations where biopirates operate, the marginalization of the victims and the lack of either academic or legal work on the issue. The discussions of Wyatt (2015) clearly points to the blatant manipulations of judicial systems and justice by corporations and countries of the North to '*camouflage environmental and human rights crimes into legal activities.*'

Wyatt (2015) adds to the discussion through the study of instances of injury caused by what he terms the '*invisible harm*' of biopiracy. The author suggests that products derived from biopiracy fall into two categories: horticulture and medicine. Additionally, the strategy employed by '*biopirates*' to render their harms invisible is supported in three ways:

- They benefit from the legal status that trade treaties bestow on their activities,
- They use the legitimacy provided by the western scientific discourse of the need for progress, and,
- They shape media messages to portray themselves as stewards of traditional knowledge.

Apart from being invisible, Imran et al. (2021) describe biopiracy as '*a silent disease*' that is hardly detectable because it does not leave traces frequently. The authors claim that powerful commercial enterprises are consistently using intellectual property rights to patent indigenous medicinal plants, seeds, genetic resources, and traditional medicines, without being regulated by any legal prescriptions. Supporting the findings of Sharma et al. (2018) in the sense that the electronic media favours highlighting environmental pollution and deforestation, while biopiracy incidents are less reported, Imran et al. (2021) conclude that:

Such a '*silent pillaging*' is rapidly depriving countries, mainly in Africa, Latin America, and Asia, that lack proper biotechnology facilities or know-how, of the means to financially support developing and sustaining biotechnological projects. Further, biopiracy seriously disrupts biodiversity conservation efforts in many countries.

The situation is additionally worsened by the fact that loosely knit indigenous communities, a constraint discussed earlier by Wyatt (2015), already burdened with the struggle to survive, are now forced to '*confront an alien network of state and private conglomerations*' that wield tremendous legal and economic power and can easily trample upon their rights, claims Das (2020).

The discussions of Goyes et al. (2017) and Goyes and South (2016) add another element to the crime of biopiracy, exposing the clear association that exists between biopiracy and what is now termed the '*Inversion of Justice.*' The authors explain how the possibility of commercially exploiting plant, animal and human genetic resources unlocked by

biotechnology has given rise to a wide range of cultural, environmental, ethical, legal and economic conflicts. Their view is that international legal agreements and treaties have disregarded the opposition to their intended goals, and gone ahead in legalizing the possibility of appropriating genetic resources and their derivative products through the imposition of patents.

However, it needs to be remembered that agreements and treaties are mere soft laws that can be ignored, and often is. An even worst situation is that in some countries the national legal framework permits not only the appropriation of natural genetic products, but also criminalizing aspects of traditional ways of life. As such, a legally approved but socially and environmentally harmful and otherwise illegal appropriation process, and most probably through a dose of corruption too, is enabled, claim Goyes and South.

The conclusion of numerous studies to this day recognise that biopiracy is nothing more than stealing or theft, and has been extensively discussed by Baruch (2010) and Wyatt and Brisman (2017). Adding a new dimension to that new form of environmental crime, Wyatt and Brisman (2017) approach the biopiracy issue from a different angle, as the '*Theft of Nature and natural resources*'. The authors claim that it remains an on-going environmental crime that contributes to global environmental degradation and destruction, and argue that even though this theft is widespread and sometimes well known, it persists because powerful actors put forward an influential narrative of denial that obstructs interventions. Leaning on the arguments of South and Brisman (2013) and White and Heckenberg (2014), the authors contends that one of the main purposes of green criminology should be to examine and analyse the causes of such environmental harms, the motivations of such thefts, and possibly establishing appropriate criminal laws to put an end to the scourge.

The leeway that exists for biopirates to operate with little inconveniences does not help in curtailing the crime, and the need to follow other avenues for criminalization, as suggested by South and Brisman (2013) and White and Heckenberg (2014) is likely to be the one that ought to be followed.

Summarising the discussions and propositions of Dunagan (2009), Robinson (2010), South and Brisman (2013), White and Heckenberg (2014), Efferth et al. (2016), Wyatt and Brisman (2017) Imran et al. (2021), Wyatt (2021), and others, the consensus is that biopiracy inevitably has to be dealt with not only through actions at various governmental levels, but more importantly within the appropriate frameworks of both national and international environmental laws. The majority of biopiracy activities are associated with international unlawful appropriation and transfers of biological resources and traditional knowledge, and in most cases these are then embodied into the intellectual property protection and patenting systems of foreign jurisdictions, simply a process of misappropriation and commodification, sanctioned by incomplete soft law systems, and biased treaty agreements.

Consequently, the urgent need to deal with the legal issues of biopiracy at the global scale becomes too obvious and pressing, and such criminal activities should be targeted at the roots of where they occur. The time has come to criminalise '*the theft of nature and natural resources*.'

Bioprospecting, a more subtle form of Biopiracy, is justified by supporters on the basis that public health, biotechnology research, new product development, and successful businesses all benefit from this kind of investigation and exploitation. According to this argument, discoveries need to be protected by strong international patent laws otherwise substantial research investments might be lost. Furthermore, it is contended that when traditional knowledge has potential but is not well served by weak intellectual property regimes or an absence of commercial models, then others have to step in. Obviously, the argument is from the profit-oriented business community's view, totally disregarding rights of ownership, and the complexities of biodiversity conservation, another factor that has hardly been the concern of businesses.

Discussing the objectives of bioprospecting, Dutfield (2001) describes it mildly as,

The practice of collecting and screening plants and other biological materials for commercial purposes.

Dutfield's definition is based on a term first introduced by Reid et al. (1993), describing bioprospecting generally as:

The exploration of biodiversity for commercially valuable genetic resources and biochemicals.

Similarly, Wikipedia defines bioprospecting conservatively as:

The exploration of natural sources for small molecules, macromolecules and biochemical and genetic information that could be developed into commercially valuable products for the agricultural, aquaculture, bioremediation, cosmetics, nanotechnology, or pharmaceutical industries.

Dutfield (2001), Reid et al. (1993) and Wikipedia appear to either omit or disregard the fact that bioprospecting is also associated with pirating indigenous bioresources and knowledge about '*plants and other biological materials.*' From these different simplified approaches to defining bioprospecting, Hayden (2003) finds that such prospecting ought to be considered as a form of appropriation through colonization where:

A '*knowledge-based economy*' only seeks profit from marginalized people and their traditional knowledge and resources.

Additionally, Hayden (2003) proposes that:

Bioprospecting is the new name for an old practice: it refers to corporate drug development based on medicinal plants, traditional knowledge, and microbes culled from the '*biodiversity rich*' regions of the globe, mostly in the developing South.

The angle from which bioprospecting is examined by scholars from various disciplines, and by international and commercial organizations may differ, but thorough analysis and assessments lead Sheldon and Balick (1995), Hayden (2003), Brown (2004), Brush (2004) Shiva (2007), Paterson and Lima (2016), Tym (2020) and others to summarise the essential concept of bioprospecting as:

When pharmaceuticals and bioprospectors extract Indigenous knowledge of medicinal plants which is later patented by medical and pharmaceutical companies without taking into account the fact that the knowledge was never invented by the patent and depriving the Indigenous community to the rights of commercial exploitation of the natural resources.

However, to emphasize on the realities of the practice, Shiva (2007) aptly describes bioprospecting through a lens of appropriation and expropriation of indigenous bioresources and traditional knowledge as:

A form of sophisticated biopiracy.....an expropriation of their collective and cumulative innovation, which they have utilized, protected, and conserved since time immemorial.

New definitions keep appearing over the years as the reality of the complexity and illegality of bioprospecting become more obvious, and new elements added to either condemn or justify the practice. Concluding their analysis on bioprospecting, more recently Imran et al. (2021) defines it as:

Bioprospecting is the act of exploring natural resources for undiscovered chemical compounds with medicinal or anti-microbial properties. Commercial success from bioprospecting leads to the company's attempt at protecting their intellectual property rights on indigenous medicinal plants, seeds, genetic resources, and traditional medicines.

The discussion of Imran et al. centres around '*undiscovered natural compounds,*' notwithstanding that as early as 2000, Sing established that '*any material within the reach of human hands has been discovered, described, and developed by one or more communities,* and Whitt (2009) claimed that the term is about '*discovering what has already been discovered.*

It has been demonstrated how generally the owners, managers and protectors of '*these resources*' hardly ever get any benefits, but are more often discriminated against and even victimized. In one study, '*When Nature Goes Public,*' Delgado (2002) and Hayden (2003) presents an ethnographic study of a prospecting plant research agreement between Mexico's National Autonomous University (UNAM) and the University of Arizona in one project, and reported in '*The Making and Unmaking of Bioprospecting in Mexico.* The project was intended to be part of a larger collaboration funded by the U.S. government's International Cooperative Biodiversity Groups (ICBG) programme. The goal of the project was designed to use Mayan folk knowledge to guide researchers to promising plants and microbes on a benefit-sharing basis. Specimens were to be screened for their commercial potential by a Welsh biotechnology company, *Molecular Nature, Inc.* The project began in 1998, but was shut down in November 2001 due to claims of biopiracy and unethical practices. That is only one of the several instances where collaboration turns into appropriation through bioprospecting, and few are brought to public notice.

Reflecting on the agreement, Hayden (2003) contends that far from a multilateral effort to support conservation and the sustainable use of biodiversity, the idea that the ICBG is trying to sell is clearly to promote the concept of bilateralism in private access to biodiversity. These contracts or bilateral agreements, known as '*bioprospecting agreements*' confirm the fact that biodiversity is no longer freely available to others and is solely and exclusively available to a select few, observes Delgado (2002) and Hayden (2003). Hayden cites the case of Peru where foreign companies/corporations have filed over 11,690 patents on natural resources traditionally used by indigenous communities, illustrating the current trend of outside transnational corporations showing an interest in traditionally-used medicinal plants and seeds, in other words pirating indigenous knowledge and property rights for profit without compensation to the rightful owners.

Bioprospecting and biopiracy have turned into a political concept since it is '*a mechanism for capitalist enrichment, ecocide, and the antithesis of sustainability*' and since '*capitalist society depends on economic changes in markets,*' claims Delgado (2002) and Breske (2017; 2018). Corporate power over knowledge of natural resources is assured because it can

exercise domination through western legal frameworks and negotiations with developing governments that need to maintain good relationships with corporations, and sometimes with corrupt government officials and even corrupt governments too, contend the authors. It again comes down to financial resources and political sway of corporations, and Delgado (2002) observes that:

Bioprospecting commercially valuable genetic and biochemical resources and subsequently patenting them, depend on the knowledge of rural and indigenous communities that have established an intimate relationship with nature since pre-capitalist times.

The study Hayden (2003) further exposes how power is often '*in the hands of transnational corporations and lobbyist groups*' with their global economy sometimes becoming larger than individual nation-state economies, and observes that bioprospecting is '*an important site for thinking about how neoliberalism works,*' in agreement with the theories of Castree (2003). The shift to neoliberalism has increased the divide between the developed and developing world, leading not only to an appropriation of resources, but also to an appropriation of knowledge, and Breske (2018) claims that:

The ideology of the market, and the omnipresence of market forces, have left an indelible mark on the western conception of knowledge.

The observation of Hayden tends to suggest that there should be a new definition to knowledge, broader and more encompassing. The struggle over who owns knowledge and the related spiral growth of economic power and influence is an ever-growing contested issue for transnational corporations. Pojman (2006) discusses how MNCs can continually grow in power and become economic driving forces, remarking that:

Unlike powerful people in a democracy, corporations are not accountable to a specific state. They are accountable only to their shareholders, who seldom are involved in day-to-day decisions.

Believing that the consequences of commodification of both bioresources and knowledge may lead to a global environmental crisis, and analyzing the complexities of biopiracy and bioprospecting, Alexiades (2003) submits that some of the key questions, '*easy to ask but hard to resolve,*' should include: *who is given and who is denied a voice? by who? why? how?* The author contends that technological, social, political, and economic processes are creating a new global perspective, defined by new opportunities and challenges and characterized, amongst others, by:

1. The validation, commoditization and politicization of genetic resources and local environmental knowledge,
2. The interpenetration of local and global actors and processes, and
3. An unfolding environmental crisis.

Alexiades (2003) concludes that the two main points of contention regarding the privatization of traditional biological and cultural resources by corporate interests are:

1. Whether such transformations are morally, ethically and politically acceptable, even in principle, and
2. If so, what mechanisms can be put into place to ensure at least some financial returns or benefits flow back to those who manage these resources.

A more crucial question would be whether mechanisms put in place would be broad enough to ensure preservation of resources for future generations. In answer to all these pertinent questions, bioprospecting remains an issue that has hardly been properly addressed to this day, and despite the advent of the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD-1992),

bioprospecting is still '*an unevenly and inadequately regulated*' activity across the world, concludes Alexiades.

Unregulated is no doubt how bioprospecting has been described on many platforms. Businesses and specially MNCs continue to collect samples without authority. They continue to deny sharing the benefits they derive from them in an equitable way, or establish policies and frameworks for ensuring continuation of the species through conservation programmes, judicious extractions, or funding. This practice appears to be still within the legal frameworks of many regions and countries, especially because of its invisibility (discussed by Wyatt, 2015), and preventing it is almost impossible even where laws exist. Bioprospectors have permeated national and international organizations working in biodiversity-rich countries, and even mixing with local communities under different capacities, and sometimes pretences too.

However, rather than condemning bioprospecting as an illegal activity outright, Mauro and Hardison (2000) point out that Indigenous Rights (IR) in general, and Traditional Knowledge (TK) in particular, are increasingly being incorporated into international law, such as the CBD. Decision IV/9 of the Conference of the Parties of the CBD accords a similar value to TK as to scientific knowledge. In 2000, the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO) member states set up an Intergovernmental Committee on Intellectual Property and Genetic Resources, Traditional Knowledge and Folklore (IGC). However, some 2 decades down the road, little progress has been made in developing an enforceable legal framework to support Indigenous Rights or Traditional Knowledge in practice, and none is expected soon in spite of the arguments of Mauro and Hardison (2000). And more importantly, international soft laws have no mechanisms for effective enforcement.

To reinforce the frailty of international agreements and soft laws, the International Society of Ethnobiology, the Society of Economic Botany, and the Biodiversity and Ethics Working Group of the Pew Conservation Fellows have additionally developed ethical guidelines regarding the use of indigenous biodiversity and knowledge. Furthermore, countries or groups of countries (e.g. The Philippines and Andean Pact countries) have or are in the process of adopting specific legislation governing bioprospecting activities. In these legislations, indigenous or local people must be given information about the ultimate use and purpose of the biological resource and they must give consent (PIC-Prior Informed Consent). In a more general sense, the CBD Conference of the Parties No. 6 at The Hague (2002) has now developed international guidelines, which pertain to access and benefits sharing. These are the so-called Bonn Guidelines on Access to Genetic Resources and Fair and Equitable Sharing of the Benefits Arising out of Their Utilization (Decision VI/24). However, guidelines do not carry the force of law, and it is business as usual for bioprospectors to this day.

The discussions and propositions of Costanza et al. (2007) add to the critical analysis and dissection of bioprospecting by presenting practical examples of how indigenous peoples and companies can reach agreements that are fair by most standards and conducive to further collaboration. The authors explain that international agreements such as the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) and the International Treaty on Plant Genetic Resources (ITPGR-2001) provide a broad framework for protecting and utilizing genetic resources. Unfortunately, such frameworks are only on paper, and more or less voluntary prescriptions.

In spite of the well-meaning discussions and proposals of Mauro and Hardison (2000) and Costanza et al. (2007), there have hardly been any reference to legal instruments in the form of hard laws to enforce what have been so far mere proposals and guidelines. What exist to this day are international ‘*soft laws*’ to supposedly regulate bioprospecting. Two of the most prominent are the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) and the Nagoya Protocol. Being merely soft laws, with complicated and tortuous enforcement mechanisms, these become practically ineffective against the power that corporations wield nationally and internationally. In analyzing the complexities and international effectiveness of these two environmental instruments, Christoffersen and Mathur(2005) dwells on the ethics of the practice rather than the obvious illegality, remarking that:

Companies continuing to collect in this way are not behaving in an ethical manner, and that is the difference between what is legal and what is right.

Additionally, what is right or ethical is a matter of judgement, while what is legal or illegal is a matter for law courts to decide, assuming that appropriate legal frameworks exist to guide the courts. The complications of bioprospecting and its invisibility at most times are not always easy to identify and assess, and the associated legal, human rights, environmental and administrative issues, and complexities have not been fully addressed yet.

Shiva (2007) claims that, and as believed by other scholars, the Nagoya Protocol could be on purpose flexible enough to allow transforming biopiracy into bioprospecting, a term that is most of the time wrongly used as an alternative to biopiracy to imply a non-exploitative way of developing and commercializing biological resources. However, in insisting to put the record straight, Vandana Shiva (2007) discards bioprospecting as ‘*merely a sophisticated form of biopiracy,*’ arguing that bioprospecting can be regarded as harmful through the way it denies local communities the self-sufficient use of their local resources. Shiva’s arguments stress on the reality that:

Bioprospecting creates impoverishment within donor communities by claiming monopolies on resources and knowledge that previously enabled communities to meet their health and nutrition needs and by forcing those communities to pay for what was originally theirs.

Shiva (2007) continues her discussion to describe how bioprospecting creates two kinds of exclusions:

1. The exclusion of communities that are not acknowledged as signatories to the agreement: when contracts are in place, agreements may be signed by a limited number of local communities that use the resource, while others are neither required to give any Priority Informed Consent or reach any Mutually Agreed Terms, thus creating inequity and potential conflicts between different communities.
2. The second exclusion takes place when a commercial actor files for a patent on ‘*knowledge,*’ given that the Nagoya Protocol often discard ownership of intellectual property as secondary.

Shiva concludes that there is hardly any difference between bioprospecting and biopiracy since:

The former’s impact on biodiversity and Indigenous cultures and local economies is the same as outright piracy. Reclaiming the intellectual commons through asserting collective intellectual property rights represents the real model of equitable benefit sharing since only the commons ensures equity and sharing.

Thus, bioprospecting leads to the '*enclosure of the biological and intellectual commons through the conversion of Indigenous communities*' usurped biodiversity and biodiversity-related knowledge into commodities protected by intellectual property rights (IPRs), claims Shiva.

Another element that has come into play to justify appropriation and expropriation through bioprospecting lies in the fact that until the 1970s, biodiversity was erroneously considered as part of the '*common heritage of humankind*.' As such, the concept was interpreted in the sense that biodiversity was a mere commodity '*of the commons*' that should be available to one and all, and without restrictions, or observations of rights of ownership of any types, or compensation/payments for collection, use, or development into commercial products; obviously a blatantly preposterous interpretation of the concept. The concept changed in the latter years to one that considers the '*common heritage of mankind*' as one that calls for the protection, and utilization of environmental goods and services sustainably to ensure continued supplies of such goods and services to present and future generations.

Taking the discussion further, and rather than simply associate bioprospecting with '*usurping community property and knowledge*,' as claimed by Shiva (2007), Popovski and Turner (2008) find there is an urgent necessity for change right across the broader frameworks of international law, justice, order, and legitimacy. As a means to that end, the author proposes the inclusion of such concepts as '*Green Criminology*,' '*Environmental Crime Prevention*' and '*Gaps between Law, Legitimacy and Justice*' for consideration, as part of the CBD's objectives. In spite of intense discussions over the years along those lines, the UN and its satellite organizations, and other relevant international organizations have preferred to tread lightly, and most of the time either in the wrong direction, or away from the problem.

Contrary to the arguments of a number of scholars, Millum (2010) questions the validity of indigenous knowledge/benefit sharing rather in a pro US-ICBGs argument, or from a Western perspective. The author argues that ownership normally implies that people may do as they wish with their possessions (within moral limits), and that intellectual property rights (IPRs) over knowledge is not valid, since no one who has the knowledge worked to acquire it. The argument of Millum is that knowledge is something that is floating around, to be harvested by anyone wishing to do so, not that it is acquired through intensive studies over time. Earlier, Gepts (2004) questioned biodiversity ownership, basing his argument wrongfully upon biodiversity being '*the common heritage of humankind*,' supporting the outdated views of Herdt (1999), and contends that:

- Biological resources belong to the public domain and are not owned by any individual, group, or state.
- Its consumption is '*non-rival*' (its use by one person does not compete with its use by another) and '*non-excludable*' (no person can exclude other persons from its use).

Since their arguments are based on the common belief of economists, it is clear that Herdt (1999), Gepts (2004) and Millum (2010) were simply arguing to justify a case for legally appropriating what belongs to others, but not themselves. In other words, legalizing appropriation and expropriation of goods and services that do have rightful owners, for profit, in other words commodifying private goods.

The long road to curtailing or even criminilising bioprospecting starts with the advent of the UN's Convention on Biological Diversity of 1992, prompted by the unsuppressed destruction of the biodiversity of the planet, and the risks to all lifeforms, including humanity. The CBD

appears to have unduly concentrated on biodiversity on indigenous lands and on indigenous knowledge rather than on the exploitative forces responsible for destroying and commodifying bioresources for profit. The next step, the Nagoya Protocol of 2010 reaffirms some the recommendations of the CBD, paving the way to TRIPs in an attempt to control the destructive activities of MNCs and states associated with such activities through forms of 'mutual' arrangements, with inputs from the World Trade Organisation (WTO) and the World Intellectual Property Organisation (WIPO).

Rather than solving problems associated with biopiracy, bioprospecting, and biocolonisation, the combined processes represent no less than licensing a slow privatizing of environmental resources and indigenous knowledge to benefit the exploiters rather than the rightful owners of both bioresources and knowledge, and by extension ensuring the health of biodiversity and the planet.

Both Drahos (1997; 2003) and Shiva (2007) contends that the WTO-TRIPS agreement's basic objective of establishing minimum international standards for Indigenous Property Rights (IPR) is based on a restrictive 'one-fits-all' approach. As such, it denies the right to enact or not to enact intellectual property rights provisions to developing countries, restricting their ability to effectively adapt national and international laws to their own socioeconomic environment and development levels.

Developed countries have widely benefited from this privilege since no minimum binding standards of intellectual property exist in multilateral relations. The TRIPS agreement stabilizes the strong inequalities in terms of bargaining power between rich and poor countries; it also reinforces the pressure exerted by US big business companies, especially MNCs during the negotiation process to universalize the western system of IP rights to the detriment of indigenous communities' intellectual property rights. In practice, the TRIPS agreement illustrates how an international agreement can help facilitate biopiracy/bioprospecting by protecting rich countries' inventions and ignoring those from the poor ones.

Further, the CBD appears to have concentrated on Indigenous Knowledge (IK) as associated with biodiversity protection, and Articles 1 and 8j summarize the needs to protect Indigenous knowledge from exploitation, and calls for the contracting states to:

Respect, preserve and maintain knowledge, innovations and practices of indigenous and local communities embodying traditional lifestyles relevant for the conservation and sustainable use of biological diversity and promote their wider application with the approval and involvement of the holders of such knowledge, innovations and practices and encourage the equitable sharing of the benefits arising from the utilization of such knowledge, innovations and practices.

The CBD must have done some gymnastics in meandering through a maze it created, mixing biodiversity, knowledge, approval, sharing, and benefits. The CBD thus creates a situation the complexities of which can hardly be reconciled, appearing to have come up with a statement that is too vague and too ambiguous to ensure biodiversity protection within areas rightfully occupied by indigenous nations. The gist of the statement tends to centre around justifying the legitimacy of bioprospecting and expropriation, as explained by Churchill (2011).

In their analysis and discussions about the objectives of the CBD, Ruggiero and South (2010; 2013) illustrate the possibility and probability of a wide range of consequences leading to

cultural, environmental, ethical, and economic conflicts. While critics refer to bioprospecting as biopiracy, international legal agreements and treaties have knowingly legalized a system of colonization and appropriation of natural resources and their derivatives through their own tailor-made soft laws, claim Ruggiero and South. The authors raise some pertinent issues associated with bioprospecting, claiming that:

These processes result in serious impacts in terms of ‘*the inversion of justice*’ and the ‘*erosion of environmental sustainability*.’

As such, claims Ruggiero and South, it should be central not only to discussions, but should be embodied in appropriate environmental and human rights laws, and international environments law and justice, in a fashion similar to the reflections of Popovsky and Turner (2008).

Discussing the technicalities of the CBD, Thornström and Björk (2007) reckon that the technical aspects of technologies can only be mastered through a totally new regime, a world order regarding biological resources, or an international regime that would:

Govern access to genetic resources and the sharing of benefits arising from their use, at the same time complying with the laws, rules, and regulations that cover access in a given country.

Discussing the same issues associated with the CBD, Hobbelink(2015) concludes that:

Although bilateral bioprospecting agreements are sanctioned by the multilateral CBD, in the vast majority of cases commercial bioprospecting agreements cannot be effectively monitored or enforced by source communities, countries, or by the Convention, and amount to little more than ‘*legalized*’ biopiracy.

Madrazo’s (2013) argument further stresses on the reality that based on colonialists forms of exploitation, currently bioprospecting allows for indigenous systems of knowledge to become publicly available and enter into:

The contested knowledge systems of colonialist corporations whose main concern is to privatize knowledge as patents on life forms.

Whereas regulating such crimes ought to have been embodied in the CBD, the UN preferred to delegate that responsibility to the Nagoya Protocol. A number of scholars agree that instead of regulating biopiracy and expropriation, the Nagoya Protocol supposedly framed to protect indigenous bioresources, indigenous traditional knowledge (TK), and rights of ownership, have left so many loopholes, inadvertently or expressly, that businesses always find an appropriate route to justify the crime of biopiracy through bioprospecting.

On an ideological level, there are deep disagreements over what a document like the Nagoya Protocol actually achieves. Potentially, the Nagoya Protocol may certainly have intended to give local and Indigenous communities a better share of the profit, and a properly enforced PIC requirement could have also helped them maintain control over their traditional knowledge and protect it against inappropriate exploitations, claim Bodegård (1997), Drahos (1997), Drahos and Braithwaite (2002) and Robinson (2015). Looking at the issues from a different angle, Biswas et al. (2012) finds that the recent ‘*conversion*’ of Indigenous knowledge into private property represents a continuation of colonial conquest masked by so-called neo-liberal market principles. The author claims there is evidence it has pushed local indigenous communities backward in their socio-economic life, raising concerns that it may increase tension between indigenous people and the State. Biswas obviously finds that the

ideological perspective of the Protocol may have serious practical implications, yet unaddressed.

In their discussions and analyses, Drahos (1997), Drahos and Braithwaite (2002) and Robinson (2015) expose how yet another limitation to the Nagoya Protocol reside in that it does not address the core issue of biopiracy: that is, patents and intellectual property rights in general. The authors find that while IPR plays a certain role in the CBD framework, it was for unexplained reasons excluded from the initial development of the Nagoya Protocol. It may be assumed the reason was primarily due to the complexities of the organizational framework of the UN, where IPR would be better regulated through the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO).

Sherman (2008) describes these '*regulatory gymnastics*' and their impacts in terms of processes leading to the inversion of justice and the erosion of environmental sustainability, similarly discussed by Ruggiero and South (2010). Discussing the objectives of the Protocol further, Rabitz (2015) finds that it is a weak response to a difficult problem, drawing a conclusion that is more of a summary of the reflections of several other scholars, in that:

The Nagoya Protocol has been described as a '*masterpiece in creative ambiguity*'.....which has '*left experts puzzled about what exactly has been agreed on for many critical issues,*'.....giving rise to....'*a range of partially conflicting interpretations.*'

Switching the discussion away from the protection of biodiversity and indigenous rights within the context of inexistent laws, and analyzing the ongoing processes of land purchases and land grabs as yet another biopiracy/bioprospecting/biocolonisation strategy to appropriate and exploit natural resources, Goyes and South (2016) remark that:

Economic strength of the North enables Northern investors to capitalise on land purchases in the South, disregarding the forced displacement of Southern indigenous communities, and Northern countries also use their economic power to transfer harm to the South, all done because of inexistent laws.

Land grabbing by powerful corporations for resource exploitation with little or no compensation, but rather indiscriminate environmental destruction has become yet another global problem, reviewed by Yang and He (2021).

Economic strength and power have no doubt resulted in a power imbalance between the powerful North and the poorer states of the South. The issue of power and effects of power imbalances between the North and the South appear to pose further problems in unjust and unlawful exploitation of resources. Discussing the concept of power, Girvan (OECD-2007) submits that power imbalances exist in a social setting, that is, when there are asymmetrical relations of power among persons, institutions, or states, and defines power as:

The ability of human agency to exercise control over its social and physical environment.

Girvan further contends that historically knowledge domination has been an integral part of the North-South unbalanced relations, confirming the earlier theory of Hayden (2003) and Bendana (2006) explaining how over the years knowledge domination has shaped North-South relations, and that today the neo-liberal theory is used to justify market-led and corporate-dominated globalization. Discussing how free trade agreements within the so-called globalized economy further create and accentuate a power imbalance between multinational corporations (MNCs) and the indigenous communities holding traditional knowledge and resources, both Bendana (2006) and Hayden (2003) concur that the issue of

power imbalance between North and South has been worsened by institutionalized dependency in the South.

The struggle over who owns knowledge and the related economic power is growing for transnational corporations. This stems from the fact that MNCs can continually grow in power and become economic driving forces. Additionally, they weave tremendous political influence and are most of the time protected by political regimes. As Louis Pojman (2006) aptly points out,

They are also given protection not afforded ordinary people through their infinite political and legal resources and act as decentralized global forces.

The patenting of property remains yet another issue of contention. Brad Sherman (2008) contends that the crucial objective of patenting centres on property, and particularly intellectual property, which is paradoxically absent from the Nagoya Protocol, in spite of the fact that it is the core of the problem that the protocol tries to address. However, the Protocol appears to favour the right to patent over the right of ownership, and as such not only accentuates imbalances of various forms, but paves the way for legal appropriation. In his discourse on the patenting of plants and botanical innovations, Brad Sherman (2008) points out that:

One of the defining features of modern patent law is that the invention is able to be treated as a separate and distinct object which is unconnected to the environment where it was produced. Importantly, it is this decontextualization of the invention that enables patents to circulate so freely and quickly, for them to become part of the commercial currency, to appear on the balance sheets of companies, and to be traded around the world.

Supporting the arguments of Sherman (2008), Boateng (2011) remarks that patents on plants and human genetic material '*are protected within TRIPS, while local and Indigenous knowledge, such as those included in Ghanaian folklore are not*', concluding that TRIPS does not acknowledge indigenous communities' rights to their own traditional knowledge. However, it allows Western companies the possibilities to patent scientific findings based on such knowledge. That points to a neocolonialist logic that defines resources differently depending on their possible proprietors, and Boateng concludes that:

Countries and groups that seek protection for these kinds of knowledge are also countries and groups that have been historically disadvantaged internationally and whose goods and knowledges have long had the status of raw material. Even where such knowledge is produced in line with Western conventions, it is still often treated as raw material.

However, Robinson (2015) proposes that an alternative interpretation would be that the Nagoya Protocol is simply a strategy to promote property creation at the expense of local natural and cultural values. Similar to the claims of Biswas (2012), the Protocol has often been accused of contributing to a '*neoliberalisation of nature*' as it promotes privatization, commodification, and marketization of natural resources, through the patenting system, claims Robinson,

In a discussion about what he terms the '*Propertization of nature,*' and in support of the proposition of Robinson, Fredriksson (2017) claims that another limitation to the Nagoya Protocol is it does not address the core issues of biopiracy and bioprospecting: that is, patents and intellectual property rights in general. Fredriksson (2017; 2021) explains how and why the patenting and commodification of biological resources and traditional knowledge became a contested phenomenon as early as the 1990s. The reasons, contends the author, is because the practice comes in many guises, including:

- It can be conducted by universities working in collaboration with local communities, or
- By small commercial research companies or by multinational pharmaceutical corporations, or
- Some may call it biopiracy while others prefer the term bioprospecting or biodiscovery.

Fredriksson finds the choice of words both interesting and significant, since they not only imply different ways to conduct and distribute the revenues from patenting of biological resources, but also different ways to look at the legitimacy of biopatents. Consequently, those who have been militating for legal prescriptions rather confusing international agreements have ground to justify their demands.

Discussing the relationship between bioprospecting and patenting of indigenous bioresources, in a thesis about what he terms ‘*The Global Quest for Green Gold*, Das (2020) claims that the Nagoya Protocol was supposedly to be instrumental in cementing the promise made by the CBD regarding equitable profit distribution between the contracting parties, and refers to two appropriate but contentious articles:

- Article 1: In case products are derived, access to genetic resources, financial support and technology transfers must be undertaken. It advocates active engagement with technical and scientific research and development, urging the involvement of host countries
- Article 5(5): Urges benefit-sharing with the knowledge holding groups.

The Protocol goes a step further by laying down the tools to deal with issues of ambiguity regarding beneficiaries and disputes between several communities sharing genetic resources across borders. However, the Protocol’s foundation appears to be based on promises rather than on explicit and implicit legal prescriptions.

Analyzing the patenting system in depth, Breske (2018) finds the scientific theoretical framework supporting the patent system is pathologically ignorant of the living reality of the natural world, claiming that:

The natural world or any life form cannot be reduced in theory or practice, as is the current model, because it is relational, contextual, interactive, complex, diverse, distinct, multidimensional, adaptive, self-healing and creative (*passim*).

Supporting the arguments of Breske (2018), Sakellaridis (2020) and other scholars similarly inclined, including Das (2020) and Shiva (2020) conclude that:

The introduction of patenting laws worldwide has opened the Pandora’s box. The patent legislation has encouraged the appropriation of genetic resources and associated knowledge for the production of commercial agricultural and pharmaceutical goods.

And in support, analyzing and discussing bioprospecting and the patenting of nature by corporations Sakellaridis (2020) observes that multinational corporations operating in developing countries have repeatedly, consistently and unlawfully claimed ownership of nature and indigenous knowledge systems by means of patents, turning the biodiversity of the commons into private, commercialized property. The author further observes that:

Such appropriation of indigenous resources for financial gain, with scarcely any recognition or compensation, is just one of the latest forms of colonialism, the centuries-old practice of affluent, technologically advanced nations exerting economic dominance over poorer, resource-rich countries.

In spite of arguments otherwise, there appears to be another school of thoughts that justifies appropriation and expropriation through frameworks that support bioprospecting, including such instruments in place as patenting of genetic resources and indigenous knowledge. Discouraging on '*Intellectual Property and Bioprospecting*' Gebru (2018) asks whether legal intervention is necessary to regulate the relationship between the knowledge-holder communities and users of traditional knowledge (TK), which represents the knowhow, skills, innovations, and practices of indigenous people and local communities. Gebru obviously refers to the contention that the knowledge that indigenous peoples and local communities developed over generations should be considered as part of the '*public domain,*' free of '*encumbrance.*'

Within such a belief, there should not be any legal requirement or business responsibilities by which recognition would be given to or benefits flow back to the source communities, otherwise the rightful owners of such knowledge and its sources. In opposition to the general objectives and Article 15 of the CBD, such reasoning should be considered as pretentious. Such contemplation would obviously work to the benefit of businesses, and be totally unacceptable to the owners of both the knowledge and the resource.

Such contentious beliefs have led the governments of Brazil, India, China, and others to enact national laws restricting access to the genetic resources and traditional knowledge within their borders, and the mechanisms adopted discussed by Cotier and Panizzon (2005). There has also been much opposition to bioprospecting projects in several parts of the world. The Leticia Declaration (1996), the Kimberley Declaration (2008) and the Nibutani Declaration (2008) consider the knowledge and genetic resources of the concerned communities to be the basis of their self-determination. For instance, in 2009, the Maasai Intellectual Property Initiative in East Africa was formed to deter companies from using the tribe's name and plagiarizing their traditional design without a licensing agreement. As a result of the Initiative, the Maasai tribe received 5 per cent of the retail sales as royalty from Koy Clothing. Whether that represents just compensation is yet to be assessed. The Initiative further hopes that fashion firms like Louis Vuitton, that have incorporated the tribe's motifs into its clothing line and are raking in millions, would be coaxed into transferring its Maasai related trademarks to the Initiative (discussed by Brindle and Florman, 2021).

While most discussions about bioprospecting appear to dwell on administrative and political issues, the legal aspects become overshadowed. Rules and regulations certainly exist regarding bioprospecting, but when it comes to laws, the world has to content with soft laws, and remains in the grips of corporations through instruments such as patents, IPR rules and others. Breske (2017; 2018) explains how rather than concentrating on appropriate environmental and human rights laws, the powerful business community of the North has monopolized legal structures to the extent that:

Devaluation, objectification, and disregard for short-term consequences to the particular life-form and for long-term consequences to the life-systems are the operative programme behind patents and IPRs.

The obvious route to follow would be through enforceable laws, and the arguments and propositions of Breske (2018) and Martinet (2019) regarding appropriate and enforceable international legal instruments that would resolve issues that continue to plague indigenous bioresources and traditional knowledge should lay the foundation for that new direction.

Biocolonisation

One Indigenous author, Laurie Anne Whitt (2009) formulated the following definition of biocolonisation:

Diverse forms of extractive biocolonialism where valued genetic resources and information are actively sought, '*discovered*', and removed to the microworlds of biotechnoscience. There they are legally transformed into the private intellectual property of corporations, universities and individuals, rendered as commodities, and placed for sale in genetic marketplaces.

While Whitt (2009) claims that the term is about '*discovering what has already been discovered*,' Shiva (1997) contends that biocolonisation is simply the expropriation of indigenous biological resources and not much different from '*biopiracy*.' Other scholars and critics apply the broader term '*biocolonialism*' to:

The range of practices that extend colonialist logic to the acquisition of human and plant organic materials, genetic '*data*', and medicinal knowledge.

Segen's Medical Dictionary (2012) defines biocolonisation as:

The commandeering of knowledge and biological resources from an indigenous people without compensation.

And, according to the Wiktionary:

The term biocolonization is used to describe the combined control of genetic and agricultural resources by a few multinational firms, which holds a powerful weapon for the invasion of cultures. Biocolonization is thus regarded as a real threat facing large sectors worldwide, particularly when it affects human food.

Definitions repeatedly centre on appropriation of knowledge and resources, control over genetic resources, the extension of colonization, and the role of powerful corporations in these solely for-profit activities. In particular, it is claimed that biocolonisation highlights the marked continuities between European colonialist practices of land and resource appropriation, and research practices within what Laurelyn Whitt (2009) calls the '*new imperial science*' which:

Marked by the confluence of science with capitalism and acting in the service of western pharmaceutical industries enables the appropriation of indigenous knowledge and resources at a prodigious and escalating rate.

Aided and abetted by the Western legal system, and most strikingly by the rise of intellectual property law, knowledge has undergone a steady process of commodification, claims Whitt (1995) in her discussion on '*Cultural Imperialism*.' Under such a situation, then biocolonialism emphasizes the role of both economic and science policies where valued genetic resources and information are actively sought, '*discovered and removed to the microworlds of biotechnoscience*,' explains Whitt, observing that:

The commodification of knowledge and of genetic resources that biocolonialism facilitates is sharply at odds with the web of prescriptions and proscriptions that guide the process of knowing within indigenous contexts.

Whitt thus associates biocolonisation with a new generation of the former type of imperial colonization, that is neocolonisation. From the philosophical point of view, Whitt (2009) describes biocolonisation as:

The cultural, political, and social ramifications of a '*new imperial science*' embedded in and at the service of the western capitalist system. It is derived from the scientific practices of late-eighteenth and nineteenth-century science that justified the expansion of empires through the '*oppression and exploitation of indigenous peoples*.'

The main objectives to what created such a new form of colonization and exploitative practice that is depriving the less developed countries of their resources, mainly in the geographical South, is the idea of claiming ownership, legal or illegal, ethical or unethical, of bioresources and indigenous knowledge through patents and trademarks, viciously defended by international trade organisations and multinational groups. However, for many traditional farmers or indigenous groups, owning a constantly evolving and changing organism is illogical and immoral as is assigning ownership to one person instead of a community of users.

Today, colonization itself is regarded as an age-old process of theft and control facilitated by doctrines of conquest that claim a country or land as empty, with little or no considerations for the millions of indigenous people that have been living there from times immemorial, and kept their natural environments (biodiversity) in its natural state through judicial use of its products and services. Posing as the self-proclaimed '*discoverers*' of crops, medicinal plants, genetic resources, and traditional knowledge, these biocolonisers thus become the new '*legal owners*,' turning nature and life processes into private property. As private property, it is alienable; that is, it can be owned, bought, and sold as a commodity, resulting in a legitimized but unlawful and unethical process of thievery today commonly known and discussed as '*biocolonialism*.'

The processes of appropriation, expropriation and commodification of indigenous knowledge and of genetic resources through biocolonialism have been extensively discussed (Bronwyn, 2006; Harry, 2009, 2014; Whitt, 1995, 2009;2010, 2020 Deibel, 2012; Chisenbu and Chisenbu, 2020). The authors are in agreement that such practices facilitated by biocolonialism is sharply at odds with the web of '*prescriptions and proscriptions that guide the process of knowing within indigenous contexts*' as proposed by Whitt (1995). They also clash directly with the responsibilities toward the natural world that many indigenous peoples have historically assumed. Most scholars contend that the ideology that sustains biocolonialism remains rooted in the neo-positivist assumption of value neutrality and in a practice of value bifurcation, which together enable it to deflect ethical and political critiques, or even opposition. As such, the marginalization of indigenous knowledge systems is facilitated and thereby providing a legitimate rationale for biocolonialist practices, claims Whitt (1995; 2009).

The discussions of Debra Harry (2009, 2011) expound on how and why the biocolonisation process requires access to, and ownership of the world's genetic resources (both human and non-human) for the development of new genetic products and processes that profits the developed countries of the North. As such, Harry states that:

Biocolonialism extends the reach of the colonial process into the biomes and knowledge systems of Indigenous peoples in the search for marketable genetic resources and traditional knowledge. Nearly everything that we hold collectively, and value as land-based societies and peoples, is at risk of misappropriation and subject to the global market in genetic resources, including Indigenous foods, medicines and even our traditional knowledge developed by our ancestors and passed down from generation to generation over millennia.

Apart from its hold on indigenous biodiverse resources, biocolonisation extends into the development and commodification of genetically modified organisms (GMOs) such as genetically modified seeds, crops and other living organisms. The commercialisation and release of GM seeds have proved to be a likely threat to food security, and have profound implications for the cultural and spiritual relationships that indigenous peoples have with their traditional foods and medicines. Furthermore, GMOs may potentially cause irreversible

impacts to natural living organisms and the environment (reviewed and discussed by Domingo, 2016). At the core of the biocolonial process is the control, manipulation and ownership of life itself, and the ancient knowledge systems held by indigenous peoples, claim Whitt (2009) and Harry (2011).

Taking the discussion on biocolonisation further, Harry (2011) asserts that biocolonialism extends the reach of the colonial process into the biomes and knowledge systems of indigenous peoples in the search for marketable genetic resources and traditional knowledge. Harry's discussions focus on the intersection of international standard-setting debates related to genetic resources and traditional knowledge, and indigenous peoples' advocacy in the assertion and protection of their rights in international fora. The author claims that:

Indigenous peoples' cultural heritage – including our knowledge and biodiversity – should not be subjected to the intellectual property regime and that recognition be given to the prior, inherent and inalienable rights of Indigenous peoples, consistent with our right of self-determination.

However, and in spite of discussions of numerous scholars to the contrary, the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples (2007) states in Article 31(1) that:

Indigenous peoples have the right to maintain, control, protect and develop their cultural heritage, traditional knowledge and traditional cultural expressions, as well as the manifestations of their sciences, technologies and cultures, including human and genetic resources, seeds, medicines, knowledge of the properties of fauna and flora.

The discussions of Newcomb (2011) regarding the declaration further stresses on the hypocrisy of the UN, leading to the observation that even when it recognises that there is such a thing as '*indigenous science and technologies*' and that the same should be legally protected, the UN actively participated in the Nagoya Protocol, engineered TRIPS, IPR and other instruments that would actually deny indigenous people such rights. It is unfortunate that flimsy international agreements and soft laws can never guarantee compliance, as observed by Hayden (2014), especially where powerful actors are involved. After analyzing the UN Declaration, Churchill (2011) concludes that it is '*a travesty of a mockery of a sham,*' and as such:

It not only fails to fulfil the aspirations of those who pursued such an articulation during the last quarter of the twentieth century, but reflects a radical disjuncture from previous codifications of the right to self-determination in international law.

However, rather than wait for international efforts for protection of their resources, some countries have started reacting with their own measures. The discussions of Robimson (2010) reveals how several governments, particularly from biodiverse developing countries, have started developing their own initiatives for '*defensive*' and '*positive*' protection of traditional knowledge and bioresources. These initiatives, explains Robimson, even if limited by their territorial scope may link into broader initiatives and provide useful examples that may ultimately be adopted by other countries that have similar concerns. However, progress in that direction appear to have been slow.

In spite of such efforts of developing countries, discussed by Whitt, Harry, Shiva and Robimson, the analysis of Petitjean (2005), Mgbeoji (2006) and Kerr (2014) claim that what still remains rooted in present day forms of imperialism, and in the minds of neocolonizers remains the archaic belief that '*land existed in order that it might be claimed; it did not have value in simply being; it was a means, not an end.*' The contention was and still is that native peoples were all that stood in the way of a seemingly endless plethora of natural resources

that can be plundered, leading to the observation of Shiva (1997), .supported by South (2013) that:

The scale of the illegal exploitation and thievery continues and has expanded since the substitution of '*European Empires*' by the more aggressive '*Multinational Corporations*,' now busy continuing the exploitation of resources of other nations.

As much as imperialism and colonization regarded the less developed countries as primitive, according to the discussions of Shiva (1997, 2007) indigenous knowledge has further been viewed as remaining primitive, or localized until MNCs produce wealth from what they have found. As a result, Shiva contends that:

Such knowledge is disempowered through its cooption by the MNCs and wealthy nation states and then legitimized when attached to the legacy of Western knowledge and technological advances.

Through bioprospecting, biocolonisation, and patents, the global '*free*' market allows these corporate practices to establish a form of biocolonialism, which becomes a continuation of previous imperialism as a technologically-advanced, biologically-controlled hold on indigenous communities, claims both Whitt and Shiva. Accordingly, biodiversity has been redefined as '*biotechnological inventions*' to make the patenting of life-forms appear less controversial. Power for transnational colonizers, previously grounded in colonial assumptions of race, gender, and domination, is now based on the value of resources and knowledge under biocolonialism, observes Shiva (1997; 2007)

At what stage during the processes of colonization *per se*, did biocolonisation and scientific colonization proper became part of such processes is unclear. The common agreement is it has most likely been creeping in when the importance and value of biological resources of the South, and indigenous knowledge regarding such resources gained importance and recognition by the industrial North, forever seeking development of new products. In fact, what the North discovered was that the South was a vast store of bioresources and knowledge which was at hand to be plundered.

The criminalization of biopiracy, its cosmetization into bioprospecting, and efforts to justify and legalise appropriation and expropriation through biocolonisation has taken the long route through a series of mostly international political prescriptions, supported by trade and commercial impositions, and embodied in ineffective environmental soft laws. As such, a new jargon came into play, including Traditional Knowledge (TK), Indigenous Rights (IK), Intellectual Property Rights (IPR), access and benefit sharing (ABS), prior informed consent (PIC), Plant Patents (PP), Plant Breeder's Rights (PBR), genetically modified organisms (GMOs), and the list goes on.

The UN appears to have set the pace in its attempts to regulate exploitation of resources through agreements and soft laws, while the business community through the World Trade Organisation ((WTO) sets the rules embodied in prescriptions, constraints and impositions. The Convention of Biological Diversity (CBD-1992) came into force with the following objectives or goals:

The conservation of biological diversity; the sustainable use of its components; and the fair and equitable sharing of benefits arising from genetic resources.

The CBD is the first multilateral treaty regime that addressed the issue of preserving the planet's biological resources. It is also the first convention to establish the sovereign right of a state over its natural resources, and its responsibility to facilitate access to those resources.

The CBD's objectives are

1. To conserve biological diversity,
2. To promote the sustainable use of its components, and
3. To achieve fair and equitable sharing of the benefits arising out of the utilisation of genetic resources.

Two issues immediately come to attention:

1. Access to these resources to who and under what conditions, and
2. Sharing of benefits with whom and under what terms.

These are probably the obvious loopholes that the CBD left open, knowingly or by omission, allowing manipulations by businesses, especially MNCs and governments of the North. According to Debra Harry (2009), executive director of the Indigenous Peoples Council on Biocolonialism (IPCB), *the CBD was enacted at a time when it became obvious that genetic resources held tremendous value.* Harry observes that the states involved in negotiations have been:

Asserting sovereignty over genetic resources, without acknowledging that sovereignty is not absolute. In reality, Indigenous Peoples are the holders and owners of much of the world's biological resources, and traditional knowledge.

In discussing the '*benefit sharing*' provision of the CBD, Ismail and Fakir (2004) find that even when the CBD mandates that source nations should receive some compensation or benefit for sharing knowledge and resources, what this means in terms of practice is less clear, even if the CBD stipulates that,

States have sovereign rights over their own biological resources and that those resources are no longer freely available to others.

In fact, the CBD only recognizes states as sovereigns over genetic resources and ignores the proprietary rights of indigenous peoples in the same territories. The fact that indigenous people are still owners of '*much of the world's biological resources, and traditional knowledge*' is simply because they have been able to manage both through judicious systems that excluded commercialization and commodification, explains Harry (2011).

Treading carefully, the CBD opts for the reconciliatory path of protecting and sharing, but omits to dwell on rights of ownership and exclusiveness of use and disposal. However, how to reconcile protection of biodiversity with commercial exploitation of bioresources may have represented problems associated with conflicts of interests.

To palliate such a dilemma, the Nagoya Protocol came into being in 2010 to take over the responsibility of regulating bioresources, with the objective of:

Establishing a framework that helps researchers access genetic resources for biotechnology research, development and other activities, in return for a fair share of any benefits from their use.

Analyzing the essence of the Protocol, Harry (2011) contends that it must first meet standards consistent with the internationally accepted rights of Indigenous Peoples, and if it does not, there will be a situation where,

The protocol will facilitate the misappropriation of genetic resources from Indigenous lands and territories, and alienate the traditional knowledge implicated in benefit sharing schemes.

It appears the Protocol has simply enabled the '*misappropriation of genetic resources from indigenous lands*'. Harry (2011) further observes how the CBD's main effort in resorting to the Nagoya Protocol focused purely on how to '*elaborate and negotiate an international regime on access to genetic resources and benefit sharing,*' or in building the highway for bioprospecting and biocolonisation. The purpose of the Nagoya Protocol appears to lay the ground rules not for states to access and share the benefits from the utilization, but rather to enable appropriation of genetic resources and associated traditional knowledge, or in other words legalizing misappropriation, claims Harry.

It is most unfortunate that the Protocol has achieved just that, as reflected in the observations of Saez (2020). Following the negotiations at the United Nations Convention on Biological Diversity in Nagoya, Japan, Saez (2020) of International Property Watch contends that indigenous peoples '*are being left with a bitter taste*' from the text of a Protocol that should have protected them from misappropriation of genetic resources rather than openly allowing the more powerful nations/corporations to legally appropriate such resources. In other words, '*legalizing thievery appears to have been the objective of both the CBD and the Nagoya Protocol,*' claims Saez.

As a follower to the CBD, in 1994 the Agreement on Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights (TRIPS), an international legal agreement between all the member nations of the World Trade Organization was signed and became effective in 1995, requiring WTO member countries to develop legal frameworks to protect varieties of plant and animal resources in two systems:

1. For agricultural contexts and
2. For pharmaceutical, chemical, textile, or other commodity contexts.

The main objectives of the TRIPS Agreement are:

1. To establish adequate and effective levels of protection for intellectual property rights, and
2. To reduce distortions and impediments to international trade from differing standards of protection.

In fact, the WTO established itself as the '*Protector*' of knowledge and genetic resources, short of implying the '*Proprietor*.' The WTO, however, remains vague in its intention to protect through failing to elaborate on whether such protection is for the benefit of humanity, or for exclusive protection of the profits of the business community. The main objectives of TRIPS can be further summarized as:

To avoid patents being issued for inventions that are not genuinely new (erroneous patents)....to help ensure that inventors have complied with countries' regulations on receiving permission to access the biological resources and on sharing the benefits with the owners of those resources.

The ubiquitous balancing act in the entirety of the TRIPS Agreement resulted in the call to harmonize the interests of the developed and developing nations, and has been captured in the WIPO-WTO (2003) declared objective of the TRIPS Agreement to the effect that:

The protection and enforcement of intellectual property rights should contribute to the promotion of technological innovation and to the transfer and dissemination of technology, to the mutual advantage of producers and users of technological knowledge and in a manner conducive to social and economic welfare, and to a balance of rights and obligations

However, it becomes clear that the main objective of TRIPS is to ‘*unbalance a system of rights and obligations*’ to the advantage of businesses. As a result, Ismail and Fakir (2004) contends that the main entity protecting indigenous knowledge and biodiversity, the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), does not afford adequate protection against either the WTO or TRIPS, which ignore indigenous rights. Such protection from the CBD would have included supporting involvement in indigenous-led alliances, and stronger domestic laws to protect against international patents from third parties. The failure of the CBD in that area prompts Whitt (2009) to declare that:

Communal indigenous knowledge needs to be shared on a multigenerational basis within the community to survive and not through directives from third parties.

Apart from being ‘*ubiquitous*’ and ‘*controversial*’ the many aspects of the TRIPS Agreement have been variously critically analyzed, and it is worth noting the summary provided by McCoy (2005), describing the agreement as:

A charter for the protection of northern knowledge-based industries that want to strengthen their grip on the global control of knowledge.

Equally controversial is the effect of TRIPS on the achievement of the CBD's objectives, and on sustainable development generally, which led Bautista (2007) to comment that:

The Agreement on Trade Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights (TRIPS) created within the framework of the World Trade Organization (WTO) poses a contentious discord between developed and developing nations. The criticism that TRIPS is nothing more than a modern vehicle of Western imperialism encapsulates the perception that the TRIPS is inimical to the interests of developing countries.

As many countries considered this counterproductive in protecting their bioresources, in early 2000 many changed their laws to protect these resources more in accordance with the 1992 Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD). However, the relationship between the objectives of the CBD and intellectual property rights (IPRs) is yet another controversial subject of continuing debate. Shiva (2007) claims IPR laws, under the development of TRIPS and the World Trade Organization (WTO), ‘*have unleashed an epidemic of the piracy of nature’s creativity and millennia of indigenous innovation.*’

Transnational corporations are taking advantage of slight ‘*innovations*’ on traditional knowledge to maintain many of their IPRs, continues Shiva, and together, IPRs and TRIPS, work ‘*to suppress indigenous peoples’ ability to control their traditional way of life.*’

Could it then be assumed that from the inception of the CBD up to the Nagoya Protocol, and through the many other instruments put in place in between, the fabrics of biocolonisation were being weaved? In an analysis of the fabrics of colonization/colonialism in general, and its tentacles, Whitt (1995; 2010) comments that:

Colonialism encompasses the interlocking array of policies and practices (economic, social, political and legal) that a dominant culture can draw on to maintain and extend its control over other peoples and lands.

The deeply offensive and culturally destructive nature of biocolonialist practices can only be fully appreciated by measuring how profoundly they clash with many of the values and commitments that characterize and distinguish indigenous knowledge systems, claims Whitt (1995; 2009).

As such, biocolonisation is in many aspects more of the same practices of the former type of imperialism and colonization that less developed countries have witnessed in history, and Whitt claims that:

It is simply a continuation of the oppressive power relations that have historically informed the interactions of western and indigenous cultures, and part of a continuum of contemporary practices that constitute forms of cultural imperialism.

Moving a step forward from imperial colonization, biocolonisation has consequently matured into new ideological, political, and practical structures of the '*new imperial science*,' allowing the appropriation of indigenous knowledge and biological resources for the benefit of Western industries and corporations through scientific developments, declares Whitt (2009; 2010). Similar to the theories of Vandana Shiva (1997), Whitt contends that biocolonialism is merely,

A type of neocolonialism and cultural imperialism allowing the perpetuation of dominance and oppression through the exploitation of indigenous peoples for profitable gains.

The harms that imperialism and colonization have caused to poorer countries and nations are still being evaluated and debated to this day. Regarding colonization and the harm it has and continue to cause to indigenous systems, Pyenson (1993) discusses what is termed the '*Civilising Mission*' of colonizers, and concludes that the mission, or imperialism/colonization process indeed moved from being cultural to a more scientific enterprise. Patrick Petitjean (2005), adding to the discussion on the '*Civilizing Mission*' observes that:

Local knowledge systems were destroyed: the progress of science in a colonial context produced new knowledge but also acculturation and ignorance. In nineteenth century France, science replaced religion as the motive for colonization, with a mission to conduct humankind to a higher stage of evolution.

However, and perhaps contrary to the statement of Petitjean (2005), colonizers of the age of imperialism resorted to both religion, to convert the natives, and science to exploit their resources and knowledge by driving the fear of God into them. Whitt (2010) explains how later historians of science have documented the vital role of late eighteenth and nineteenth century science as a part of statecraft, a means of extending empires, and no doubt as an instrument of colonization too, and Whitt observes that:

In extractive biocolonialism, the valued genetic resources, and associated agricultural and medicinal knowledge of indigenous peoples are sought, legally converted into private intellectual property, transformed into commodities, and then placed for sale in genetic marketplaces.

The observations of Pyenson (1993) and Petitjean (2005) have been analyzed and expanded further by Hira (2015) in his discussion about the transformation of colonialism from Theology to Science. Hira contends that colonization has been transformed to fit into the modern context of exploitation for profit with the new objective of shifting knowledge production from the search for the truth in the Holy Scriptures, to discovering the laws of nature and society and man's ability to understand these laws. The arguments of Hira becomes relevant when science tries to deal with colonialism and tries to understand the nature of that peculiar system within the framework of the new imperialistic system of governance of the North.

Discussing his thesis on '*Science, Colonialism, and Indigenous Peoples*' Whitt (2009; 2014) produces a critical examination of these developments, and demonstrates how relations

between Indigenous and Western knowledge systems continue to be shaped by the dynamics of power, the politics of property, and the inconsistencies of existing laws. Similar to the observations of Whitt, the discussions of Sahai (2013) lead to the conclusion that:

What is so often referred to as indigenous knowledge is actually a knowledge system distilled from generations of scientific work anchored in rural and tribal communities. It is different to the Western system of empirical, lab-based science, but is equally valid and efficacious.

What Sahai implies is that the existence of indigenous science and technology should be recognized, and protected, as proffered by United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples (2007). However, that has never been the case, or intention since the problem stems from the belief that indigenous peoples are merely the holders, not owners, of communal knowledge. What is not considered is their territorial rights to the resources on their lands, and the sources of such knowledge, observes Harry (2009) claiming that the main problem with biocolonialism remains what she terms:

The manipulation and ownership of life itself, and the ancient knowledge systems held by Indigenous peoples.

As opposed to the motives and views of biocolonisers, Veracini (2014) believes the need for self-sustainability hinges on the ability of indigenous peoples to use traditional knowledge and not be '*under the thumb of neoliberalism and its confining and self-serving patent and intellectual property laws.*' At the most basic level, the communal rights of indigenous peoples need to be universally recognized in order to protect and neutralize the detrimental effects of corporate greed under neoliberalism, contends Veracini.

According to Lorenzo Veracini (2014), biocolonisation as opposed to the traditional imperialistic forms of colonization results in that:

It is the least visible types of colonial subjugation, and like informal colonialism and trade imperialism, are the most resistant to change

Discussing the association of dependence cultivated by imperial colonialists of a past era, with present day unlawful exploitation of resources of other nations, Patnaik (2015) contends that dependence is a key aspect of colonialism. Nevertheless and strangely enough, when it comes to food, the author claims that it is the coloniser that is dependent on the colonized in several ways. This transmuted relation creates the need for, and accentuates the particular significance of the use of contrivances by the coloniser that once again reverse this dynamics of dependency by re-inventing indigenous knowledge, or rather transforming that knowledge into a science-based one, commodifying it through patents, and selling it back to the indigenous people, explains Patnaik.

In his discussion regarding biocolonisation, Barker (2019) contends that appropriation and patenting indigenous knowledge also means taking away the autonomy of those who initially and rightfully control their biodiversity or traditional knowledge. Despite the claims that bioprospecting is not actually theft, and only a gathering of resources that are available to all, biopiracy, which stems from the initial bioprospecting endeavours has become a lucrative market for pharmaceutical companies now relying on biocolonialism to thrive in their profit-oriented activities, with the least concern for biodiversity protection and indigenous rights.

The patent system as seen today is a recreation of the colonial system of extracting resources of a marginalized group by a more powerful (or wealthy) entity. Consequently, Breske (2018) claims that the western legal system and international intellectual property law has commodified indigenous knowledge and traditional resources. Thus, biocolonisation is an

‘aggressive instrument of corporate globalizers’ who profit from knowledge appropriation and endanger ‘intergenerational sustainability for indigenous communities,’ contends Breske (2019).

Science is also central in biocolonialism, the extractive process by which genetic material and associated knowledge of indigenous peoples are being turned into commodities and sold. Stewart et al. (2022) observe that while Europeans came as explorers and settlers to these distant indigenous lands to pursue their social and economic interests, if ever Indigenous peoples impeded those interests, they were forcibly moved or otherwise eliminated by whatever means necessary. Analyzing the scientific meanings of colonization and their implications for indigenous peoples, the authors contend that because science is implicated in sociocultural colonization and its very material and ongoing social and economic impacts, despite its benefits, much-vaunted (by colonisers, in particular), for Indigenous peoples. Science is also central to biocolonialism, as reflected in the extractive process by which genetic material and associated knowledge of indigenous peoples are being turned into commodities and sold.

A more environmentally aware or ‘green’ criminology has been slowly and consistently developing, and as is the case with work paying attention to the impact of corporate bio-agriculture and the exploitation of food production. Walters (2004) pioneered work in this general area by reviewing a New Zealand report on genetic modification and examining the social, economic and ecological risks of genetically modified (GM) foods; Robinson and Raven (2017) have elaborated on efforts along the same lines in Australia.

Reactions against scientific biocolonisation may have been slow over the years. In 2018, Palau ratified the Nagoya Protocol (UNEP-2018) to safeguard its biodiversity, after making a well-meaning statement which, however, has failed to carry the legal force it requires, but nevertheless reflects on the practices of scientific colonization:

If a scientist or a company collects biological specimens in another country, takes them back to their country, conducts research and later makes millions by creating products using those genetic resources – that’s stealing. The practice is known as bioprospecting.

However, opposition to scientific colonization has been growing in several parts of the world. The plan to introduce, or rather impose GMO crops on developing countries of the South, would certainly be the next stage in Scientific Colonization. However, opposition has been building up, and in 2018 the Alliance for Food Sovereignty in Africa (AFSA-2008) made a formal and decisive statement:

It’s time to say NO to their failed solutions. It’s time for Africa to shake off the neo-colonial influence and shape her own healthy, resilient and culturally appropriate farming and food systems.

The question of legitimacy has been raised many times in discussions about biocolonialism, and the inadequacies of existing soft law instruments have similarly raised concerns. In his analysis of ‘*The Protection of Biodiversity and Traditional Knowledge in International Law of Intellectual Property*,’ Curci (2009) concludes that:

The relationships between international intellectual property treaties, the United Nations international environmental treaties (first and foremost the CBD), the relevant customary norms and soft laws form a complex network of obligations that sometimes conflict with each other.

Curci further observes that while the first set of treaties creates private rights, the latter affirms the sovereignty rights of States over genetic resources and related knowledge, thus creating international regimes of exploitation of the same. Whether these soft laws intentionally allow such conflicts need to be discussed, and Drahos (2014) remarks that after colonization, indigenous people faced an extractive property rights regime for both their land and knowledge, and the symbolic function of international intellectual property laws have simply assisted states ‘*to enclose both indigenous peoples’ knowledge and biodiversity through biocolonialism.*’

So far all discussion have centred on Biopiracy cum Bioprospecting cum Biocolonisation on land, where the question of ethics, rights, and legality arise, but all three practices, common in the open oceans beyond and within international waters have attracted little attention. However, issues associated with biopiracy, bioprospecting and biocolonisation of ocean and seabed natural resources have been analyzed from various angles and discussed by Arico and Salpin (2005), Scovazzi, (2006), Salpin and Germani (2010), Germani and Salpin (2011), Salpin. (2013) and Vierros et al. (2015, 2016)

Discussing current existing international legal frameworks, including the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS-1982), The International Seabed Authority (ISA-1994), the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD-1992), intellectual property rights instruments and regional marine related legal and administrative instruments, Arico and Salpin (2005, 2013), conclude that none adequately address the conservation of, access to, and benefit-sharing related to seabed resources. The gaps highlighted by the authors include:

- The uncertain legal status of deep seabed genetic resources,
- Whether deep seabed genetic resources fall under the regime of living resources in the High Seas under UNCLOS,
- The lack of an international acceptable definition of Bioprospecting,
- Treatment of information and research results, also in the context of possible conflicts between CBD-UNCLOS-ISA-WOC and intellectual property rights instruments,
- The legitimacy of asserting intellectual property rights over resources deemed of public interest, and what constitutes a patentable invention with regard to genetic resources,
- The principle for and modalities of sharing of ensuing benefits, and
- Institutional, legal, ethical and moral prescriptions to supervise and control commercial exploitation of seabed resources.

What Arico and Salpin (2005, 2013), Scovazzi (2006) and Salpin and Germani (2010) are concerned about is that what has been tolerated on land, to the detriment of biodiversity, communities and local knowledge will not take the same route. The authors elaborate upon important practical implications of exploitation and utilisation, unresolved legal and economic issues and concerns for owners of sampled material, and for third-party users.

What should also not be overlooked is the likely depletion of and harms caused to marine biodiversity, especially in the open oceans, or ‘*the commons*’ contends Vierros et al. (2015, 2016). What appear to always creep into discussions are issues regarding ‘*patentable inventions*’ and ‘*benefit sharing*’ claim the authors. Analyzing the first, regarding inventions, one should question whether what nature produces should fall within the category of human inventions. Regarding benefit sharing, it would be contentious to even imagine that owners should share benefits accruing from resources that they own, unless such resources are sold as raw materials for further transformation. It needs to be also noted that businesses through

the power of corporations are tightening their grips on ocean/seabed resources through the creation of their own institution, the World Ocean Council (WOC-2010).

Will the argument of '*Common Heritage of Humankind*' be once more waved as a passport to ocean and seabed resources? Or should **Legal Instruments** be the next obvious route to follow to see an end to biopiracy, bioprospecting and biocolonisation?

Environmental Crime Prevention through appropriate and enforceable national and international legal prescriptions remains the obvious route to follow since international efforts through agreements and soft laws have failed to protect traditional knowledge, cultural expressions and rights, and indigenous bioresources. In analyzing biopiracy, bioprospecting, biocolonisation and the harms and injustice it has been and still is causing to bioresources and communities in some parts of the world, it becomes obvious that soft laws and management prescriptions instituted by the CBD, the Nagoya Protocol, the WTO, the WIPO and other international organisations have failed to address the core of the problem. The power of businesses to appropriate and expropriate through their own prescriptions and backed by the WTO and WIPO has been out of control for too long, and consequently a new direction ought to be followed.

Attempting to follow that new direction, the discussions of De George (2005) elaborates on how the assertion of ownership of nature underpins the over-exploitation of the earth and its resources. That realization has begun to attract some attention in criminology via the reappraisal of traditional notions of crimes, injurious behaviours, and social harms caused by the activities of transnational corporations and governments. A more environmentally aware or '*green*' criminology is now developing with some work paying attention to the impact of corporations on bioresources, bio-agriculture and the exploitation of food production, declares the author.

Popovski and Turner (2008) were amongst the first scholars to suggest changes right across the broader frameworks of international law, justice, order, and legitimacy, suggesting that concepts of '*Green Criminology*' and '*Environmental Crime Prevention*' would better address the situation and should be included within revisions or additions to the United Nation's CBD, the Nagoya Protocol, and subsequent propositions.

Communities and governments have been calling for an international legal instrument providing *sui generis* protection, discussed at length by Halewood (1999) and Drahos (2004). Additionally, Martinet (2019) explains how an appropriate and enforceable international legal instrument would define what is meant by traditional knowledge and traditional cultural expressions, who the rights holders would be, how competing claims by communities would be resolved, and what rights and exceptions ought to apply. Working out the details is complex and there are divergent views on the best way forward, including whether intellectual property-type rights are appropriate for protecting traditional forms of innovation and creativity, concludes Martinet.

In spite of what has been shown over decades of analysis and discussion, the common business and capitalistic belief is anchored on the assumption that even though economic development harms the environment, the magnitude of the harmful association decreases over the course of development, a proposition and belief that remain unsubstantiated either scientifically, or economically, or socially. The opposite appears to be the stark reality. As

such, Jorgensen and Clark (2012) argue to the contrary, and referring to ‘*the treadmill of production theory*’ of Schnaiberg (1980), re-iterate how the strong relationship existing between environmental harms and economic development will remain constant or possibly increase through time, once the balance between extraction and production become skewed. Available information proves that the stage has been reached, as evidenced by the overshooting of planetary boundaries recently observed, (Stockholm Resilience Center, SRC-2022).

Foster (2000) and Jorgenson and Clark (2012) strongly support the theory of Schainberg (1980) in that depletion/extraction/exportation of resources from less developed nations with biocapacity surpluses, as part of the global capitalist development agenda, will result in a global consumption deficit, and thus contrary to the belief of the business/capitalistic model of economic development. Obviously, the capitalistic agenda ignores the theories behind the Planetary Boundaries of the Stockholm Resilience Centre (2009), or *The Limits to Growth* of The Club of Rome (Meadows and Meadows, 1972), or *The Earth Charter* (2000). Whether ignorance of international prescriptions should also be criminalized is another matter for further discussion.

In addition and in support of his arguments, Foster further claims that, as an example, the Kyoto Protocol of 1997 on global warming, designed to limit the greenhouse gas emissions of nations, has done nothing but encourage many business and economic advocates to resorting to improved technology as the main escape from the present environmental mess. Foster (2000) intuitively states in his analysis that:

The magic bullet of technology, however, is by far the favorite, seeming to hold out the possibility of environmental improvement with the least effect on the smooth working of the capitalist machine.

For the purpose of consolidating green criminology related to activities involving biopiracy, bioprospecting and biocolonisation, elaboration of a green perspective within the domain of criminology through the study of rights, justice, nature, and globalised society has become an urgency. From the studies and propositions of Popovski and Turner (2008), Dunagan (2009), Robinson (2010), Brisman and South (2013; 2019), Stretesky et al. (2013a, 2013b), Efferth et al. (2016), Goyes (2018a, 2019a), Weiss (2019), Lynch (2018; 2020), Goyes et al. (2021) and Imran et al. (2021), and scores of other scholars, resorting to appropriate frameworks within both national and international environmental laws as the solution needs further analysis, discussions, and more importantly application.

The two issues that have been at the centre of discussions about biopiracy, bioprospecting and biocolonisation are those regarding ownership of bioresources and knowledge within the concept of property rights. Knowledge becomes intellectual ‘*property*’ in a process that has been described as bioprospecting or biopiracy, explain Shiva (1997; 2008), Goyes (2016) and Goyes and South (2016, 2017). The assertion of ownership of nature underpins the over-exploitation of the earth and its resources, which has started to attract the attention of criminologists via the reappraisal of traditional notions of crimes, injurious behaviours, and social harms caused by the activities of transnational corporations and governments, claims Goyes and South.

Picking up from the discussions and conclusions of Shiva (1997), Ferris (2004) proposes that various legal mechanisms are available to protect indigenous bioresources and traditional knowledge, but the departing point is that such legal protection would require a response that

is ‘*pragmatic, yet innovative.*’ The consensus is that conventional legal machineries as proposed by the CBD, the Nagoya Protocol, the WTO and WIPO have failed. Consequently, Ferris proposes investigating other avenues, including the concept of *sui generis* rights, also proposed by Gopalakrishnan (2002), for protection by way of human rights law, or through cultural and environmental criminal laws within the context of green criminology, discussed by Brisman and South (2013), Goyes (2018a, 2018b), and Imran et al. (2021).

The studies of Stretesky et al. (2013), which includes legal and extralegal environmental harms, contends that to define biopiracy, bioprospecting, biocolonisation and the army of prescriptions and proscriptions that accompany them as acts of green crime, such activities should be appropriately defined as:

Acts that cause or have the potential to cause significant harm to ecological systems for the purpose of increasing or supporting production.

Following up from the propositions of Stretesky et al. (2013), Ruggiero and South (2013) contends that since environmental harm takes place within the overarching context of a distinct global political economy, and due to the ‘*invisibility*’ of such crimes, it should be noted that:

Much work has exposed specific types of criminal or harmful environmental actions or omissions. What is less common, however, are examples of study that locate these harms, crimes, injustices and corrupt practices within the context of an explicit theoretical understanding of the state or economic relations.

The discussions and analyses of Harry (2011), Goyes and South (2016) and Goyes (2018a, 2018b) elaborates on how in attempting to exploit plant, animal and human genetic resources, research and the practices of biotechnology have unlocked a wide range of cultural, environmental, ethical and economic conflicts, all bordering on environmental criminal activities. The authors find that even when such activities are classified as bioprospecting by supporters of biotechnological development and innovation, critics refer to them as a crime of biopiracy from the realities on the ground. Most of the criticism and opposition are justified by the fact that international legal agreements and treaties have disregarded opposition and legalized the possibility of appropriating genetic resources and their derivative products through bioprospecting and the use of patents, favouring businesses to the detriment of nature.

Reddy and Lakshmikumaran (2015) appear to be more concerned about whether scientific research is becoming more bureaucratized, notwithstanding that it may actually become more politicized, or even commercialised in the case of bioprospecting and biopiracy. The authors propose that a global treaty may remain a distant reality, while the immediate concern should be the steps taken by the global community to protect access to biological resources in the name of protecting traditional knowledge and world biodiversity. Referring to the Indian experience, the authors propose that intellectual property rights, like real property rights, should be justified through two of the most popular legal theories, namely:

1. The natural rights theory, and
2. The utilitarian theory.

However, the earlier discussions of Gopalakrishnan (2002) about the Indian situation proposed that there should simply be a *sui generis* law in India, and the proposition for an international legal instrument providing *sui generis* protection for indigenous people’s rights has been discussed and elaborated upon by Ferris (2004) and Goyes (2016).

Analyzing the legal framework in Columbia, as an example, Goyes and South (2016) and Goyes et al. (2021)) expounds on how the appropriation of natural genetic products by bioprospectors has also led to a strategy to criminalize aspects of traditional ways of life. Thus a legally approved but socially harmful land-grabbing process has been enabled, a reflection on the return of the ancient concept of *Terra Nullius* (discussed by Fitzmaurice (2007)).

Fitzmaurice (2007) dwells on the ancient colonizer's exploitative policies, still practiced today by both states and corporations in indigenous territories, concluding that:

On top of occupation justified on the grounds of *terra nullius* (literally 'no man's land,' that is uninhabited land or land inhabited by 'barbarians') came the creation of institutions designed to develop and exploit the work of indigenous persons

Given the persisting situation, criminological exploration should aim at combating the environmental harms that affect the geographical and the metaphorical South, contends Goyes (2018a). Analyzing the rising conflicts in the interactions between human beings and the natural environment, seen from a Southern perspective with a focus on the victimisation of the South, Goyes elaborates on how, for example, the ETCO Project typifies the crime of biopiracy and provides for punishment of up to 12 years in prison for biopirates. Brazil claims to be losing some \$287 billion annually from biopiracy and illegal markets, not withstanding losses of biodiversity and genetic resources.

Further to discussions regarding the concept of green crimes and green criminology, there have been suggestions for also considering the theory of '*cultural criminology*,' developed by some scholars, as within the context of green crimes. A point of reference would be the definition of Stretesky et al. (2013), which draws on the political economic theory in environmental sociology and arguments concerning the ecologically destructive tendency of capitalism. According to Brisman and South (2013) and as an addition to the findings of Ferris (2004), the concept has not been well developed, and with a few exceptions, little work attempting to explicitly or implicitly integrate cultural criminology with green criminology/corporate crimes and vice versa have been completed.

However, the authors propose the concept of a '*green-cultural criminology*,' as an approach that seeks to incorporate a concern with the cultural significance of the environment, environmental crime, and environmental harm into the green criminological framework. Through such a framework, the authors intend to demonstrate how cultural criminology is, at some levels and in some instances, already enshrined in the concept of green crimes and green criminology. In other words, both cultural harms and the ensuing environmental crimes within the green crimes context often interact, harming both cultures and the natural environment.

Analyzing the situation in Argentina, Weiss (2019) prefers to concentrate on environmental crimes committed in the global south, and supports the project for a '*Critical Green Southern Criminology*' or '*Southern Green Criminology*' perspective proposed by Stretesky et al. (2013), Brisman and South (2013) and Goyes (2018a,b; 2019a,b). According to Weiss, the concept would permit understanding how and why green criminology must ensure that the environmental crimes and harms affecting the lands of the peoples of the Global South are brought to the forefront.

In particular, claims Goyes, a green southern criminology might be understood as:

The science that is attentive to the dynamics and contexts of the global south and that is formed from the epistemological power of the marginalised, impoverished, and oppressed.

The proposition, supported by Brisman, South and Walters (2018), has been fine-tuned by Goyes (2019) to mean:

The production of green criminological knowledge attuned to the differential world (material, symbolic and epistemological) existent in the global south, thus preventing the universalization of Western theories.

On the other hand, Weiss (2019) explains that green harms committed by multinational corporations have however been persistently associated with under-criminalisation. Referring to cases brought to court as a result of the efforts of NGOs and affected communities, the author informs that from 2000 to 2008, out of the 1,254 criminal cases for environmental crimes, only five ended with a conviction. Given the unfairness of a criminal system that lacks efficiency, Weiss concludes that:

However, the criminal justice system does not focus on the harm produced by the corporations, acting with the support or the indifference of local and national governments,

Indigenous peoples, their cultures and territories, have been subjected to continuous victimisation, plunder and genocide throughout history, or at least '*history*' as created by and written from the North, claims South (2007; 2013), Rugierro and South (2010; 2013), Long et al. (2012) and Goyes and South (2021). Since contact with colonisers, these many different peoples have suffered legal and illegal forms of direct, structural, and symbolic violence.

The world has reached a stage where the pressing nature of environmental threats, such as: climate change, land-grabbing, biopiracy, animal exploitation and human environmental victimisation are pushing the entire world to seek alternatives to prevent environmental damage in every corner of the globe. As a means of control and curtailment, Goyes (2016; 2018a,b; 2019a,b), Weiss (2019) and Goyes et al. (2021), with contributions from others, propose that the concept of '*Southern Green Criminology*,' which focuses on the threat the Western world poses to the rest of the globe, and how Western imposed ideas of progress are damaging the planet, especially the southern hemisphere, should be at the forefront for consideration. The general consensus is that in the past years, the attention of green criminologists has been directed at the Global South as the geographical site that experiences the severest consequences of harmful environmental practices.

The authors propose a conceptual and theoretical basis for enhancing an ethical and non-colonial engagement with this underdeveloped field of work, concluding that that to counter the under-representation of indigenous explorations and contributors in criminology, a broader transformation of the discipline will be necessary.

In establishing the connections between the political and economic approaches to green crimes (GC), Lynch (2018; 2020) and Lynch et al. (2019) contend that environmental sociology, theories of metabolic rift, unequal ecological exchange, scientific evidence on planetary boundaries, and ecological footprints in an era of anthropogenic-driven global ecological collapse should all be considered. Lynch and co-workers further propose that in analyzing widespread human and nonhuman green victimization, academic disciplines must pay increased attention to ecological disorganization, ecosystem destruction, and excessive production/consumption, all in more than one way associated with biopiracy, bioprospecting and biocolonisation.

Meanwhile, Goyes and South (2021) lament that criminology, the discipline concerned with studying instances of criminality, harm, and victimization has largely remained, Untouched by or indifferent to serious crimes and systematic attacks that have increased mortality, denied rights and destroyed traditional ways of life.

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